

REVIEW

Open Access

Mapping the research landscape of blockchain and crowdfunding

Abderahman Rejeb^{1*}, Karim Rejeb², Andrea Appolloni³, Suhaiza Zailani⁴ and Mohammad Iranmanesh⁵

*Correspondence:
abderrahmen.rejeb@gmail.com

¹ Faculty of Business and Economics, Széchenyi István University, Győr 9026, Hungary

² Faculty of Sciences of Bizerte, University of Carthage, Tunis, Tunisia

³ Department of Management and Law, Faculty of Economics, University of Rome Tor Vergata, Via Columbia, 2, 00133 Rome, Italy

⁴ Department of Management, Faculty of Business and Economics, University Malaya, 50603 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

⁵ La Trobe Business School, La Trobe University, Melbourne, Australia

Abstract

Blockchain technology and crowdfunding (CF) have emerged as disruptive forces in the finance and entrepreneurship landscape, potentially transforming traditional modes of capital raising and investment. This study investigates the intersection of blockchain technology and CF to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of research through a systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis. By examining 219 publications sourced from Scopus, this study employed descriptive statistics, article co-citations, and keyword co-occurrence to identify key bibliometric indicators, themes, and trends. The findings reveal a surge in research activity related to blockchain and CF, emphasizing initial cryptocurrency offerings, financial technology (Fintech), and the role of blockchain in improving transactional efficiency, disintermediation, and venture capital CF. Keyword co-occurrence analysis reveals diverse research themes, including smart contracts, fundraising campaigns, sustainable entrepreneurship, and Islamic Fintech. Based on the findings of this analysis, several implications and directions for further investigation are highlighted. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to analyze the intersection of blockchain technology and CF using scientometric techniques systematically.

Keywords: Blockchain technology, Crowdfunding, Initial coin offering, Fintech, Entrepreneurship

Introduction

At the turn of the millennium, the digital financing of enterprises and projects has undergone a remarkable evolution due to the development of novel financing methods (Butticè and Vismara 2022; Rejeb et al. 2023c). The emergence of crowdfunding (CF) as a novel approach to raising capital has attracted considerable attention, presenting a viable substitute for conventional digital financing sources such as bank loans and venture capitalists (Baumgardner et al. 2017; Camilleri and Bresciani 2022). Conceptually, CF relies on the power of the Internet and social media to enable entrepreneurs, creators, and artists to collect funds from numerous individuals who collectively contribute money to support the ventures or projects in which they believe (Bargoni et al. 2022a, b; Belleflamme et al. 2014). Owing to the Internet's extensive availability and reach, CF emerged as a game-changing digital financing method in the early 2000s. According to several scholars (Block et al. 2021; Butticè

et al. 2022; Vismara 2022), this democratized financing model has since evolved into various forms, including equity-, debt-, reward-, and donation-based CF, each meeting the needs of different sorts of projects and investors. The rapid expansion of the CF industry is evident in numerous successful campaigns on popular platforms such as Kickstarter (Dai and Zhang 2019), IndieGoGo (Gallemore et al. 2019), and GoFundMe (Zhang et al. 2021), which collectively raised billions of dollars for diverse projects worldwide.

Despite the remarkable growth and success of CF, several challenges undermine the efficiency and sustainability of digital financing (Delina 2023; Gomber et al. 2017). For example, CF is hampered by a lack of transparency and accountability (Nehme 2018). Without proper monitoring and reporting mechanisms, CF platforms may suffer from a lack of credibility and trust among potential investors. This could result in a significant decline in the number of supporters ready to invest in CF campaigns, ultimately threatening the sustainability of the digital financing industry. Furthermore, the high failure rate of crowd-funded projects, often due to unrealistic expectations (Turan 2015), inadequate planning (Weinstein and Barden 2017), or unforeseen complications (Ghobadi and Mathiassen 2024), can dissuade potential investors and undermine the credibility of CF platforms. Finally, the absence of standardized regulations and guidelines across jurisdictions can exacerbate these concerns because they can hamper cross-border collaborations (Hughes 2021) and expose investors to legal uncertainty (Collomb et al. 2019).

To address these issues, blockchain technology has emerged as a decentralized, distributed ledger system that underpins cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin and can fundamentally reshape the CF landscape (Baber 2020a; Cai 2018; Jain et al. 2024; Zhu and Zhou 2016). Blockchain provides transparent (Rejeb et al. 2021d), immutable (Asaduzzaman et al. 2020), and secure records of all transactions (Jeyasheela Rakkini and Geetha 2021), enabling stakeholders to track and verify the flow of funds in real time (Mas and Chuen 2015). By incorporating smart contracts (i.e., self-executing agreements encoded on the blockchain), CF projects can automate processes, reduce administrative costs, and ensure that funds are disbursed only when predetermined conditions are met (Annenkov et al. 2020; Dal Mas et al. 2020; Gavrilova et al. 2020). Consequently, this can enhance transparency and accountability and mitigate the risks associated with mismanagement and fraud (Baber 2019). The decentralized nature of blockchain technology offers significant benefits in terms of regulatory compliance and cross-border transactions (Collomb et al. 2019). This technology provides a single unified framework for recording and verifying transactions, facilitating compliance with diverse regulatory requirements, and streamlining cross-border CF initiatives (Gomber et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2020). Moreover, the tokenization of assets on the blockchain allows for the development of digital securities that can be easily traded and transferred (Basu et al. 2022; Laatikainen et al. 2020). This enhances liquidity and creates fresh investment prospects for issuers and investors. Therefore, integrating blockchain technology into the CF ecosystem promises to foster a robust, transparent, and efficient financing landscape. By overcoming existing limitations and challenges related to CF, blockchain can enhance investor confidence and participation and drive the growth and diversification of the CF industry. The synergistic combination of CF and blockchain can accelerate the democratization of access to

capital (Arefjevs et al. 2020; O'Dair and Owen 2019), empowering entrepreneurs, innovators, and creators to bring their ideas to fruition.

Despite the growing body of literature on the intersection of blockchain and CF, few reviews exist on this subject. For example, Zhu and Zhou (2016) investigated how blockchain technology can be used to address issues related to equity CF in China, particularly emphasizing transparency, data security, and integrity. Their results indicate that blockchain can provide cost-effective and secure methods for recording stocks and shares, streamlining transactions and transfers, facilitating peer-to-peer transactions, creating voting systems, and assisting regulatory actions within the sector. Nguyen et al. (2021) examined how the blockchain can be utilized in socially oriented CF platforms to promote social value creation. The authors also identify factors that could facilitate or hinder blockchain implementation on social CF platforms. Cai (2018) conducted a systematic review of financial technology (Fintech) research between 2010 and 2018 and emphasized the lack of focus on economics and finance research pertaining to CF and blockchain technology. According to the authors, blockchain technology can eliminate the need for intermediaries in certain financial domains owing to its trust-based characteristics. Hua et al. (2019) reviewed Fintech research and emphasized the need to investigate the societal impacts of Fintech and provide a detailed analysis of CF and blockchain. Bhatt et al. (2022) focused on the effects of technological advancements such as Fintech, digitalization, blockchain technology, artificial intelligence, and machine learning on the financial sector. Their study also examined the acceleration of these technological developments due to the COVID-19 pandemic and proposed potential avenues for future research using bibliometric analysis and thematic literature review techniques. Finally, Sun et al. (2022) evaluate Fintech's progress by employing a bibliometric analysis to identify the basis of information technology, the driving force of financial innovation, and the assurance of financial oversight.

Existing literature often examines certain facets of blockchain and CF, such as their implementation in equity CF or their contribution to the development of social value. However, a comprehensive analysis of this phenomenon is lacking. This study addresses this deficiency by conducting a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of CF and blockchain research. It attempts to provide a complete and unbiased knowledge structure of the blockchain-CF research area (Rejeb et al. 2023b). This study differs from prior bibliometric studies by examining the junction of CF and blockchain rather than focusing on Fintech (Li and Xu 2021; Pandey et al. 2024). Consequently, it provided a more precise and insightful analysis. Specifically, this study addresses the following research objectives:

- To analyze the evolution of scholarly research on CF and blockchain, identifying key developments and shifts in focus over time.
- To identify countries or regions, journals, and academic institutions that have significantly contributed to the CF and blockchain literature, highlighting the most influential studies and researchers in the field.
- To uncover the latest trends and emerging topics of interest in CF and blockchain research, providing insights into current research directions and potential future developments.

This study aims to improve the understanding of the current state of CF and blockchain research, identify areas for further investigation, and serve as a valuable resource for scholars and practitioners interested in combining these two innovative financing methods. In summary, this work pioneers a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of CF and blockchain research, filling a notable need in existing research. By delineating the significant contributions and prevailing trends in this domain, this study offers a lucid guide for future investigations and underscores the potential of blockchain technology to revolutionize the CF environment.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. “[Conceptual background](#)” section provides the conceptual background of the review, and “[Methodology](#)” section describes the research methodology. Subsequently, “[Analysis of descriptive results](#)” and “[Bibliometric analysis](#)” sections present descriptive and bibliometric analyses, respectively. Further, “[Discussion and future research directions](#)” section discusses the findings and directions for future research. Finally, “[Conclusions](#)” section concludes the study, highlighting its implications and limitations.

Conceptual background

Crowdfunding

The CF concept refers to a method of raising capital by soliciting contributions from numerous individuals (Rejeb et al. 2023c; Rejeb et al. 2024b; Rossi and Vismara 2018; Xia et al. 2024). CF pushes businesses and people to provide financial support to the initiatives they find most compelling, linking creators with creative ideas to backers who have the means to invest in those ideas (Kuppuswamy and Bayus 2018). In addition to easing businesses’ capital shortages, CF can help enterprises avoid financial conundrums by dispersing the associated financing risks. Several CF subtypes have emerged in recent years (Meyskens and Bird 2015; Paschen 2017). In consumer CF, manufacturers showcase their goods and services to prospective buyers through CF platforms to encourage those buyers to participate in CF activities and consolidate dispersed market demand. By soliciting pre-orders from customers, business owners can raise the capital they need to manufacture a product before it is made. According to Belleflamme et al. (2014), once CF proves effective, a company may apply differential pricing strategies for CF consumers and regular consumers. While both types of consumers aim to fund product manufacturing, consumer CF is based on current products, whereas pre-sale CF is based on raising all the necessary funds for production without any pre-existing products.

CF has emerged as a novel financing approach that complements conventional funding methods (Baber and Fanea-Ivanovici 2022; Rejeb et al. 2023c), offering significant benefits in fostering business sustainability (Böckel et al. 2021), expediting capital growth (Eldridge et al. 2021; Li and Wang 2019), and encouraging innovation (Bargoni et al. 2022a, b; Turan 2015). Recently, scholars have integrated CF into several domains. For instance, Reza-Gharehbagh et al. (2021) investigated CF’s role in fostering indigenous innovation within supply chain finance. Furthermore, Zhang et al. (2022) examined how equity CF affects the co-creation of value in closed-loop supply chains and offered solutions to achieve a balance between economic and environmental value. The results indicate that equitable CF may reduce excess income for manufacturers, but it can increase value for the consumer, retailer, remanufacturer, and closed-loop supply chain, as well

as the environmental value. CF encounters various difficulties, including the persistent challenge of information asymmetry, which hinders sustainable development. This issue can result in problems such as delayed decision-making, adverse selection, and insufficient fundraising performance (Campino et al. 2022; Saadat et al. 2019). In particular, pre-sale CF poses greater information asymmetry challenges because it obtains monetary support from consumers before the products become publicly available. To ensure CF sustainability, disclosure policies can help minimize information asymmetry and enable wider choices for CF participants (Kim et al. 2022). Additionally, incorporating new digital technologies into CF platforms can improve information sharing between funders and fundraisers, increase information transparency, and mitigate the adverse effects of information asymmetry during CF initiatives (Wu et al. 2022).

Blockchain technology

Blockchain technology has emerged as a disruptive innovation, revolutionizing various sectors and underpinning the rise of CF platforms (Nguyen et al. 2021; Saadat et al. 2019). Blockchain is a decentralized and distributed ledger that securely records digital transactions across a computer network (Treiblmaier 2018). It was conceptualized by Nakamoto (2008) as the underlying technology for Bitcoin—a type of cryptocurrency independent of any regulatory authority or financial institution (Musleh et al. 2019). Swan (2015) delineates the salient features of blockchain, including decentralization, immutability, transparency, and security. These characteristics have been instrumental in the technology's widespread adoption across multiple industries (Tapscott and Tapscott 2016), including supply chain management (Azevedo et al. 2023), transport (Koh et al. 2020), healthcare (Rejeb et al. 2021e), tourism (Rashideh 2020), and agriculture (Kamilaris et al. 2019). Decentralization involves removing intermediaries from transactions by leveraging blockchain technology, which operates on a peer-to-peer network to encourage democratic consensus process (Mougayar 2016). As described by Zohar (2015), immutability is the ability of a blockchain to record transactions permanently, making them resistant to modification. Transparency is an essential feature, as each transaction is visible to all network participants, promoting trust and accountability (Rejeb et al. 2021b). Blockchain cryptographic security measures ensure data integrity and protect networks from malicious attacks (Narayanan et al. 2016).

The financial sector has been notably affected by the emergence of blockchain technology, which can streamline processes, reduce costs, and eliminate intermediaries (Fosso Wamba et al. 2020). Blockchain technology has been pivotal in the growth and evolution of CFs. Xie et al. (2020) argued that blockchain enables the creation of trustless CF platforms, eliminating the need for third-party intermediaries and reducing transaction costs. A practical example is the Ethereum platform, which enables decentralized CF without the need for traditional financial intermediaries (Bhatia and Tyagi 2021).

Zhu and Zhou (2016) indicate that blockchain can support equity CF by providing a unified platform that offers transparency, data security, and integrity, resolves double payment issues, eliminates paper documents, reduces labor costs, and ensures compliance with regulations. For instance, platforms such as StartEngine utilize blockchain to streamline equity CF and ensure transparent and secure recordkeeping (Stekli and Cali 2020).

Similarly, Nguyen et al. (2021) noted that blockchain enhances trustworthiness and social value contribution in CF by offering a distributed ledger system that allows for consensus-based transaction verification, reduces operational costs, and prevents fraud by enhancing trust among investors and investees. This is evident in platforms such as GoFundMe, where blockchain's transparency is pivotal in building trust among participants (Sirisawat et al. 2022). Furthermore, the implementation of smart contracts—self-executing contracts with terms directly written into the code—automates the release of funds, ensuring that projects meet predefined milestones before receiving investments (Gavrilova et al. 2020). Kickstarter's exploration of smart contract technology to ensure that project milestones are met before funding is released is a case in point (Block et al. 2021).

The emergence of initial coin offerings (ICOs) and security token offerings (STOs) has bolstered the role of blockchain in CF (Meoli and Vismara 2022). These offerings allow startups to raise capital by issuing digital tokens, which can represent ownership, utility, or debt and are tradable in secondary markets (Rossi et al. 2023). Ethereum's ICO is a notable example, revolutionizing fundraising by enabling widespread public token sales. The democratization of fundraising through blockchain-based CF platforms has empowered entrepreneurs and investors alike, fostering innovation and economic growth (Bargoni et al. 2022a, b). Platforms such as WeFunder demonstrate this by allowing a broader range of investors to engage in early-stage investing (Zhu and Zhou 2016). In conclusion, the literature highlights the transformative impact of blockchain technology across various sectors, with particular emphasis on its role in facilitating and enhancing CF. The technology's defining characteristics of decentralization, immutability, transparency, and security have driven its adoption and the development of innovative applications, fostering a paradigm shift in traditional fundraising methods (Stekli and Cali 2020).

Methodology

We conducted a bibliometric literature review to assess the present state of research on the nexus between CF and blockchain technology. Scholars can use this type of review to synthesize existing academic knowledge and spark new lines of future inquiry. Rejeb et al. (2021a, b, c, d, e) state that the strengths of bibliometric reviews lie in their ability to detect and classify various papers on a certain topic, facilitate data analysis, and expose trends and patterns based on amalgamated data. Bibliometric reviews also guarantee impartiality and offer fresh insights into academic literature (Caputo et al. 2022). Using bibliometric techniques, scholars can illustrate the conceptual structure of a particular research domain and simplify the comprehension of their outcomes.

Data collection

The first step in the bibliometric review process involved determining the most appropriate database for this study. We searched the Scopus database to identify relevant publications. Scopus is widely used to analyze research fields because of its ability to manage bibliographic references and assess citation metrics (Abdollahi et al. 2021; Rejeb et al. 2021d). Furthermore, Scopus is a globally recognized scientific database, and its indexing coverage is approximately 70% larger than that of the Web of Science database (Rejeb et al. 2021d). According to Sweileh (2018), Scopus is one of the most extensive

and reliable data repositories for peer-reviewed academic journals, conference proceedings, chapters, and books spanning different subject areas and showcasing the evolution of science and technology. Our search used the title, abstract, and keyword fields and incorporated the following queries:

(“crowdfund*” OR “crowd invest*” OR “online peer lend*” OR “crowdinvest*” OR “crowd fund*” OR “peer-to-peer (P2P) lending” OR “P2P lend*” OR “peer-to-peer lend*” OR “micro lend*” OR “microlend*” OR “micro-lend*” OR “microfinanc*”) AND (block-chain* OR “block*chain*”).

We adopted an inclusive approach by analyzing numerous publications, encompassing journal articles, books, chapters, and conference proceedings. This strategy is pivotal in providing a multifaceted and interdisciplinary perspective on the topic (Rejeb et al. 2020). While pivotal in the academic literature, journal articles may not always offer a complete picture of the research landscape in areas as dynamic and cross-disciplinary as CF and blockchain technology. By integrating books, chapters, and conference proceedings into our analysis, we captured a broader spectrum of scholarly contributions, including in-depth explorations, theoretical frameworks, and latest research findings, often presented at academic conferences. Recognizing that CF and blockchain technologies intersect in various fields, including finance, economics, and computer science, a diverse literature base is essential for a holistic understanding of these areas (Basu et al. 2022; Zhu and Zhou 2016). Books typically authored by field experts provide a comprehensive overview of the subject matter (Kim 2015), while conference proceedings keep scholars abreast of the newest developments and trends (Rejeb et al. 2021a). Therefore, our approach of including various academic literature types allows for a more complete and interdisciplinary analysis encompassing diverse perspectives, research outputs, and emerging trends in the field.

We expanded our search by including all English-language publications and selecting all documents published on March 10, 2023. As we did not narrow our results to specific subject areas, the Scopus database initially returned 288 documents. This study focused on the intersection of CF and blockchain technology. To ensure the quality of the literature review and minimize bias, two authors independently screened 288 publications by considering titles, abstracts, and, if needed, the full text. This process yielded a final sample of 219 documents that were comprehensive and relevant to the research questions.

Bibliometric techniques

Following a descriptive analysis of the selected samples, we thoroughly investigated the content of the articles and their interrelationships to gain additional insights. We utilized bibliometric data and network analysis techniques to portray the structure of CF blockchain research networks using CiteSpace, a free Java-based software application that allows for the examination of co-citations, creation of visual maps, and identification of emerging patterns and trends (Chen 2006). The process began with the extraction of bibliographic data from the selected articles, including citations, references, keywords, authorship, and publication details. These data form the foundation for the construction of various networks and analyses (Rejeb et al. 2024c).

Similar to other software for science mapping (e.g., VantagePoint, Bibexcel), CiteSpace enables the generation and examination of co-occurrence networks involving

subject categories and keywords (keyword co-occurrence analysis), as well as co-citation networks featuring documents, journals, and authors (co-citation analysis). Co-occurrence analysis reveals patterns in the use of keywords and subjects, illustrating how different concepts are interconnected within a research field (Callon et al. 1991). However, co-citation analysis identifies clusters of frequently cited documents, authors, or journals, highlighting influential works and contributors (Rejeb et al. 2022a).

Furthermore, CiteSpace allows the analysis of temporal patterns within a particular field of knowledge. This includes the identification of rapidly developing topical areas and frequently cited articles or journals and significant turning points in the intellectual structure. This temporal analysis is particularly valuable in discerning how the focus of research has shifted over time, revealing emerging trends and declining interest.

CiteSpace can create bibliometric networks across various periods while identifying radical changes, emerging trends, and intellectual turning points through the visualization of burst terms and between centrality (Chen 2006). These features are instrumental in detecting new and rapidly evolving research topics. Moreover, CiteSpace offers customizable display modes such as time zone views and cluster views (Yang et al. 2019). This flexibility allows researchers to tailor their visual presentation to suit their analytical needs, facilitating a clearer understanding of complex data.

We conducted co-citation and co-word analyses to expose the intellectual structure, trace the evolution of research topics, and indicate possible trajectories for future research (Rejeb et al. 2022c). CiteSpace offers various co-citation analysis methods, including article, journal, and author co-citation analyses (Chen 2006). Article co-citation analysis helps identify how often two articles are cited together within other articles. This analysis creates networks that reveal the connections between various research works, highlighting those frequently referenced together and, therefore, intellectually related (Leung et al. 2017). It is particularly useful for identifying seminal studies and emerging trends in this field (Rejeb et al. 2022b). Nevertheless, journal co-citation analysis examines the frequency with which two journals are cited together in the literature (Suban 2022). This method provides insights into the relationships between different academic journals and can help us understand the interdisciplinary nature of research fields and the evolution of scholarly communication. Author co-citation analysis focuses on the connections between frequently cited authors (White and McCain 1998). This analysis forms networks that reveal intellectual communities or “invisible colleges” that show collaborative and influential patterns among scholars. It is instrumental in understanding the social structures and collaborative networks within a research community.

In addition to article co-citation analysis, we conducted a keyword co-occurrence analysis to identify the main hotspots in research at the intersection of CF and blockchain technology (Rejeb et al. 2020). This form of analysis is a standard approach in content analysis based on the premise that the co-occurrence of two keywords within the same set of publications implies a thematic or conceptual link between them. Keyword co-occurrence analysis is conducted by quantifying the frequency with which pairs of keywords appear within a corpus of literature in a specific research

field (Callon et al. 1991). This allowed us to map the thematic landscape of the field, highlighting the predominant concepts and how they were interconnected. This technique is based on the notion that the repeated co-occurrence of certain keywords signifies their centrality and relevance within the knowledge domain.

Additionally, this analysis was instrumental in tracking the evolution of research themes over time. This enables us to identify emerging trends, shifts in research focus, and the development of new subfields within the broader areas of CF and blockchain technology. By analyzing the patterns in keyword occurrences, we can discern the trajectory of the field and predict future research directions. In this approach, sophisticated algorithms are utilized to analyze large datasets of publications, extracting and evaluating the frequency and patterns of keyword pairs. The results are often visualized in a network graph (Rejeb et al. 2023b), where keywords and their co-occurrences are represented as nodes and links, respectively. The strength of the links indicates the degree of association between keywords, revealing the most influential topics and their interrelations. This method assumes that the most frequently co-occurring keywords represent core themes and concepts in the literature, providing a window into the intellectual structure and focus areas of the field (Mostafa et al. 2022).

Analysis of descriptive results

Distribution of publications by year

Exploring the interplay between blockchain technology and CF has gained increasing scholarly attention, as shown in Fig. 1. Starting modestly with two publications in 2015, the output increased slightly to three publications in 2016. However, 2017 saw stagnation, with only two publications, marking a period of consolidation for the scholarly community. A significant shift occurred in 2018, as the number of publications surged to 16, an 800% increase from the previous year. This rise can be attributed to the growing recognition of blockchain’s potential to transform CF, which is catalyzed by the emergence of initial coin offerings and security token offerings as novel fundraising methods (Ackermann et al. 2020; Huang et al. 2020). Research momentum continued to intensify, with publications doubling to 32 in 2019, reflecting the exploration of blockchain-based CF implications, such as the regulation and democratization of finance. The research output peaked in 2020, with 55 publications, indicating the maturation of

Fig. 1 Year-wise distribution of publications

the field. A slight decrease to 48 publications in 2021 may suggest saturation or a shift in research focus. Nevertheless, 2022 saw a rebound, with 50 publications, indicating the field’s continued evolution. As of March 2023, 11 publications suggested that the scholarly community is engaged in this domain. Overall, the annual distribution of publications revealed a dynamic research landscape characterized by gradual growth, followed by rapid acceleration from 2018 onward. Sustained interest in the intersection of blockchain technology and CF highlights the importance of this interdisciplinary field, as scholars have investigated blockchain’s potential to reshape traditional fundraising mechanisms and drive innovation.

Geographical distribution of publications

Figure 2 shows the geographical distribution of selected publications. Research on the intersection of blockchain technology and CF has revealed a diverse geographic distribution, with scholars from across the world contributing to the exploration of this interdisciplinary field. A total of 61 countries and regions contributed to this body of research, reflecting the global appeal of blockchain and CF as areas of inquiry. As shown in Fig. 2, India led the pack with 46 publications, demonstrating its status as a growing hub for technological innovation and research. The Indian scholarly community’s keen interest in this domain underscores the country’s pursuit of cutting-edge advancements in blockchain technology and CF. The United States has 38 publications, which is not surprising, given the nation’s well-established reputation for technological prowess and its deep-rooted culture of entrepreneurship (Collomb et al. 2019). The research community in the US has a keen interest in exploring the potential intersection of blockchain and CF, as it holds enormous implications for the future of financial innovation and fundraising.

Moreover, with 26 publications, China has a strong research interest in this area. As one of the world’s largest economies, China’s engagement in blockchain and CF research indicates its desire to remain at the forefront of technological advancement and explore new opportunities for economic growth (Zhu and Zhou 2016). European countries such as Germany, the United Kingdom, and Italy have also made notable contributions to the field, with 18, 13, and 11 publications, respectively. Importantly, our analysis includes contributions from African countries, although they are few in number. Specifically, six

Fig. 2 Geographical distribution of publications

African countries—Tunisia (two journal articles), Ghana (one article), Morocco (one article), Nigeria (one article), Senegal (one article), and South Africa (one article)—contributed to this research area. Owing to the relatively lower number of publications from these countries, they were grouped into an “other” category in Fig. 2. This categorization was used to maintain clarity in the data presentation, given the large number of countries involved. Nonetheless, it is crucial to acknowledge the contributions of these African nations as they represent a growing interest and engagement in blockchain and CF within the continent, providing unique insights and perspectives relevant to their specific contexts.

Other countries and regions, including Canada, Russia, Singapore, Hong Kong, Australia, Belgium, France, Malaysia, Pakistan, and the United Arab Emirates, have made few contributions to the research landscape. This wide geographic dispersion underlines the universality of the subject matter and the global relevance of blockchain technology and CF.

Distribution of publications by source

The analysis of the selected publications according to source offers valuable insights into the combination of blockchain and CF. This analysis highlights the breadth of interest across diverse research communities, including the computer science, finance, management, and sustainability disciplines. According to Fig. 3, the source with the most publications is the Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, with nine documents. This series focuses on the various aspects of network systems, showcasing the prominence of blockchain technology as a critical network innovation. This demonstrates the relevance of blockchain and CF research within the broader context of network systems, emphasizing the technological underpinnings of this interdisciplinary field. With six documents, the ACM International Conference Proceedings Series is another significant source of research. As a prestigious forum for computer science research, the inclusion of blockchain and CF research in ACM proceedings underscores the importance of these topics for the computer science community.

Furthermore, the Communications in Computer and Information Science and Lecture Notes in Computer Science series, each with five documents, establish the strong connection between blockchain and CF research and the computer science discipline.

Fig. 3 Distribution of publications by sources

These publications highlight the ongoing interest in exploring the technological foundations and potential applications of blockchain-based CF platforms. In terms of journals, *Financial Innovation*, *Managerial Finance*, and *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* published three articles each and represented the research output of the finance and management disciplines. These journals emphasize the financial and economic implications of blockchain-based CF and explore distributed verification, equity CF, ICOs, security tokens, social CF, and Fintech research (Campino et al. 2022; Domingo et al. 2020; Nguyen et al. 2021; Zhu and Zhou 2016). Finally, *Sustainability*, with three documents, demonstrates interest in this interdisciplinary field from an environmental and social perspective. Publications in this journal may explore the potential of blockchain technology and CF to promote sustainable development, foster social innovation, and contribute to the achievement of the United Nations' sustainable development goals (Y. Liu et al. 2021; Rizwan and Mustafa 2022).

Distribution of publications by institution

Table 1 lists the top ten most productive institutions in the fields of blockchain technology and CF and reveals a diverse array of academic institutions contributing to this interdisciplinary field. With 383 institutions involved, the data underscore the widespread interest and engagement of the global academic community. Singapore Management University (SMU) had the highest number of publications (5) and an impressive citation count of 539. This demonstrates the institution's significant impact on the research landscape and its commitment to exploring the applications and implications of blockchain technology in CF. SMU's focus on management and business education likely drives its interest in the confluence of these two innovative areas. Moreover, the University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA) and the University of Pennsylvania, each with four publications, exhibit strong contributions to the field. UCLA's citation count of 59 indicates that its research resonated within the scholarly community, while the University of Pennsylvania's 32 citations suggest an emerging influence in the domain. Both universities are renowned for their multidisciplinary research and strong programs in technology, finance, and management, which provide fertile grounds for exploring blockchain and CF.

Table 1 Top 10 productive institutions

Institution name	Count	Cited by
Singapore Management University	5	539
University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)	4	59
University of Pennsylvania	4	32
University of Luxembourg	4	27
Amity University	4	6
University of Cagliari	3	29
Chinese University of Hong Kong (CUHK)	3	22
University of Kuala Lumpur	3	20
University of Bayreuth	3	19
Technical University of Munich	3	5

The University of Luxembourg, with four publications and 27 citations, highlights the European academic community's engagement in this field. As a hub for finance and technology research, an institution's interest in blockchain and CF aligns with its broader research priorities. Finally, Amity University, the University of Cagliari, the Chinese University of Hong Kong (CUHK), the University of Kuala Lumpur, the University of Bayreuth, and the Technical University of Munich have made notable contributions to the field, with three to four publications each. These institutions, with varying citation counts, reflect the global and interdisciplinary nature of research on blockchain technology and CF. In summary, the global representation and interdisciplinary nature of these institutions highlight the universal relevance of this field as scholars from various backgrounds continue to investigate their potential to reshape traditional fundraising mechanisms and drive innovation.

Most cited publications

Citations are a measure of the impact of a publication. Table 2 presents the top 20 most influential publications based on the number of citations received. At the top of the list is the study by Gomber et al. (2018), with 440 citations, which introduces a novel approach for mapping Fintech innovations and discusses some domains influenced by blockchain technology, including lending and deposit services, investment, and operations management. Second, Chen (2018) studied the prospective influence of blockchain technology and digital tokens on entrepreneurship and innovation. According to Chen (2018), the emergence of blockchain has made it possible to generate digital tokens that can embody different types of assets, and has resulted in the development of a fresh fundraising technique referred to as ICOs.

Blockchain tokens possess features that make them attractive to investors worldwide, such as being global, rare, fluid, and tradable, and can be utilized to denote ownership shares in profit-sharing CF initiatives or to act as pre-orders in preordering CF initiatives. Another highly cited publication with 200 citations presents a comprehensive examination of Fintech literature, focusing on its effect on the banking sector by introducing innovative payment systems, credit markets, and insurance policies (Thakor 2020). This study also focuses on the role of blockchain in smart contracts and delivers valuable perspectives on the present status and future paths of Fintech research. The remaining studies focused on smart contracts (Huang et al. 2020; Oliva et al. 2020; Zichichi et al. 2019; Zou et al. 2021), CF and token offerings (Cai 2018; Milian et al. 2019), and payment systems (Egger et al. 2019). Interestingly, most documents were articles, indicating a strong focus on empirical research and theoretical contributions.

Bibliometric analysis

In this section, an investigation is conducted using co-citation and keyword co-occurrence analyses to detect current research hotspots and emerging trends. The results of a co-citation analysis are contextual and rely on factors such as publications, authors, and journals being studied. Unlike co-citation analysis, authors' keywords serve as the basis for keyword co-occurrence analysis (Rejeb et al. 2024e; Singh and Rejeb 2024). Both analyses were conducted on the cluster, time zone, and timeline views offered by CiteSpace to identify the key nodes and trends in the research field. In general, the larger

Table 2 Top 20 most cited publications

Num	Title	Document type	Year	Source	Number Citations
1	(Gomber et al. 2018) On the Fintech Revolution: Interpreting the Forces of Innovation, Disruption, and Transformation in Financial Services	Article	2018	Journal of Management Information Systems	440
2	(Chen 2018) Blockchain tokens and the potential democratization of entrepreneurship and innovation	Article	2018	Business Horizons	206
3	(Thakor 2020) Fintech and banking: What do we know?	Article	2020	Journal of Financial Intermediation	200
4	(Milian et al. 2019) Fintechs: A literature review and research agenda	Article	2019	Electronic Commerce Research and Applications	148
5	(Cai 2018) Disruption of financial intermediation by FinTech: a review on crowdfunding and blockchain	Article	2018	Accounting and Finance	110
6	(Zhu and Zhou 2016) Analysis and outlook of applications of blockchain technology to equity crowdfunding in China	Review	2016	Financial Innovation	100
7	(Zou et al. 2021) Smart Contract Development: Challenges and Opportunities	Article	2021	IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering	86
8	(Huang et al. 2020) The geography of initial coin offerings	Article	2020	Small Business Economics	65
9	(Oliva et al. 2020) An exploratory study of smart contracts in the Ethereum blockchain platform	Article	2020	Empirical Software Engineering	62
10	(Liu et al. 2020) What have we learnt from 10 years of fintech research? A scientometric analysis	Article	2020	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	61
11	(Block et al. 2021) The entrepreneurial finance markets of the future: a comparison of crowdfunding and initial coin offerings	Article	2021	Small Business Economics	59
12	(Momtaz 2021) Entrepreneurial Finance and Moral Hazard: Evidence from Token Offerings	Article	2021	Journal of Business Venturing	54
13	(Huang et al. 2019) Smart contract security: A software lifecycle perspective	Review	2019	IEEE Access	51
14	(Sangwan et al. 2020) Financial technology: a review of extant literature	Review	2020	Studies in Economics and Finance	39
15	(Egger et al. 2019) Atomic multi-channel updates with constant collateral in bitcoin-compatible payment-channel networks	Conference Paper	2019	–	39
16	(Domingo et al. 2020) What factors drive returns on initial coin offerings?	Article	2020	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	34
17	(Zichichi et al. 2019) LikeStarter: A Smart-contract based Social DAO for Crowdfunding	Conference Paper	2019	–	32

Table 2 (continued)

Num	Title	Document type	Year	Source	Number Citations
18	(Giudici 2018) Fintech Risk Management: A Research Challenge for Artificial Intelligence in Finance	Article	2018	Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence	31
19	(Hua et al. 2019) Current practices, new insights, and emerging trends of financial technologies	Review	2019	Industrial Management and Data Systems	30
20	(Hartmann et al. 2019) Alternative Fundraising: Success Factors for Blockchain-Based versus Conventional Crowdfunding	Conference Paper	2019	–	29

Fig. 4 Co-citation network

the number of co-cited publications or keywords, the larger the cluster, and vice versa for nodes, which denote the frequency with which a publication or keyword is co-cited.

Co-citation analysis

Cluster analysis of the document co-citation network can be conducted using CiteSpace, which classifies all cited publications into distinct groups according to their degree of resemblance to one another (Chen 2006). Publications within the same cluster tend to have comparable or consistent subject matter (Rejeb et al. 2024a). The links between the clusters can also be shown using various visualizations and statistics. Figure 4 shows the six major clusters obtained from the co-cited publications: Cluster #0 (initial coin offering), Cluster #1 (smart contract), Cluster #2 (crowdfunding platform), Cluster #3 (social media), Cluster #4 (operational excellence), and Cluster #5 (blockchain ethics). The log-likelihood ratio (LLR) technique was used to derive cluster labels from co-cited publications.

Owing to the existence of pivotal nodes, co-citation network clusters are inextricably intertwined. In Fig. 4, the nodes represent scholarly works that define the connections

between clusters. Collomb et al. (2019) combined Clusters #0 and #3 and examined whether ICOs should be subject to the same legal framework as initial public offerings (IPOs) and equity CF by drawing parallels between these three types of financing and analyzing their relative merits, weaknesses, and risks. They also examined the potential of blockchain technology as a regulatory tool to uphold the basic standards of the financial regulatory framework. Similarly, Hartmann et al. (2019) connect Clusters #2 and #4 to help businesses plan efficient fundraising campaigns and regulators use current regulatory frameworks by identifying the success and characteristics that affect blockchain-based CF and comparing them to those of traditional CF.

Information on the clusters, including their identifiers, labels, size, silhouette, mean (year), and most frequently used terms (log-likelihood ratio and p -level), is summarized in Table 3. Cluster #0 (initial coin offering) contains the most publications (25), followed by Cluster #1 (smart contract) with 22 publications, and Cluster #2 (crowdfunding platform) with 21 publications. The CiteSpace silhouette quantifies the cohesiveness of a cluster. Cluster publications are more likely to be consistent with one another if the silhouette value is closer to 1. Each of the six clusters in Table 3 has a silhouette value greater than 0.80, demonstrating the excellent quality and reliability of the cluster analysis. The average year of publication for the works clustered in the network was 2019, with the exception of Cluster #0, which included works published in 2020.

The first cluster in the co-citation network, at the intersection of CF and blockchain technology, highlights the key themes and topics that revolve around the role of ICOs in enabling new forms of entrepreneurial finance. This cluster is characterized by a set of prominent terms, including “initial coin offering,” “white paper,” “entrepreneurial finance,” “ICO success,” and “financial technology.” This cluster represents a rich body of

Table 3 The details of each cluster

ID	Label	Size	Silhouette	Mean (Year)	Top Terms (log-likelihood ratio, p -level)
0	Initial coin offering	25	0.906	2020	Initial coin offering (9926.91, 1.0E−4); white paper (3248.35, 1.0E−4); entrepreneurial finance (2378.04, 1.0E−4); ICO success (2061.27, 1.0E−4); financial technology (1725, 1.0E−4)
1	Smart contract	22	0.811	2019	Smart contract (7284.02, 1.0E−4); initial coin offering (5675.59, 1.0E−4); fintech ecosystem (3898.17, 1.0E−4); financial technology (3669.16, 1.0E−4); fintech service (3396.03, 1.0E−4)
2	Crowdfunding platform	21	0.885	2019	Crowdfunding platform (1705.28, 1.0E−4); crowdfunding model (836.17, 1.0E−4); data breaches (771.37, 1.0E−4); third-party platform (711.94, 1.0E−4); novel blockchain (695.75, 1.0E−4)
3	Social media	11	0.901	2019	Smart contract (12,873.85, 1.0E−4); social media (1233.24, 1.0E−4); app developer (1217.89, 1.0E−4); verification rule (1198.84, 1.0E−4); transaction latency (1160.71, 1.0E−4)
4	Operational excellence	11	0.915	2019	Operational excellence (851.89, 1.0E−4); various stakeholder (778.78, 1.0E−4); formal institution (730.04, 1.0E−4); finance sector (730.04, 1.0E−4); financial regulator (656.96, 1.0E−4)
5	Blockchain ethics	6	0.873	2019	Blockchain ethics (1063.06, 1.0E−4); self-help group (761.91, 1.0E−4); microfinance institution (622.51, 1.0E−4); blockchain governance (571.17, 1.0E−4); cryptocurrency model (549.18, 1.0E−4)

research on the application of blockchain technology in CF, particularly through ICOs. ICO refers to a novel fundraising mechanism enabled by blockchain technology in which entrepreneurs can issue and sell digital tokens to investors in exchange for capital. In this regard, Chen (2018) states that, similar to CF, ICOs raise funds directly from early investors rather than via conventional middlemen such as investment bankers and venture capitalists. Huang et al. (2020) argued that ICOs enable entrepreneurs to obtain capital without worrying about compliance or relying on middlemen. According to the authors, the demand for ICOs comes from digital entrepreneurs who want to start a company or expand an existing one with the help of investors who value their technical, programming, or financial expertise. White paper, another prominent term in this cluster, is a crucial component of the ICO process and serves as a detailed prospectus outlining the project's vision, goals, and technical specifications (Kolbe et al. 2022). The inclusion of the term "entrepreneurial finance" in this cluster reflects the close relationship between blockchain-based CF and the broader field of entrepreneurial finance, as both involve the mobilization of capital for innovative ventures (Block et al. 2021). Several studies in this cluster highlight the importance of understanding the factors that contribute to successful ICOs, including the design of the token, credibility of the project team, and level of investor interest (Campino et al. 2021). The high frequency of the term "financial technology" in the studies of the first cluster suggests the broader implications of blockchain-based CF for the financial industry, as the technology can disrupt conventional modes of financial intermediation and democratize access to capital (Chen et al. 2021).

The second cluster focuses primarily on Fintech's rapidly evolving world and its potential impact on the financial sector. Studies in this cluster explore various Fintech applications such as blockchain, CF, and the use of artificial intelligence in finance (Giudici 2018). One common subtheme that emerged from the analysis of the second cluster was the disruptive potential of blockchain technology and its smart contract features. Several studies have examined the integration of blockchain into peer-to-peer (P2P) lending and CF, highlighting the potential benefits of decentralized platforms and the use of smart contracts to ensure transparency, security, and efficiency (Coffie and Zhao 2021; Lukita et al. 2020; Mbodji et al. 2020).

Legal and regulatory aspects are also pivotal in shaping the Fintech landscape, particularly through the lens of blockchain technology and digital currencies. Schwarcz (2022) emphasized the importance of understanding the regulatory frameworks governing these technologies and argued that regulatory clarity is essential for fostering innovation while ensuring consumer protection and financial stability. Moreover, Allah Rakha (2023) delved into the legal challenges and compliance requirements faced by Fintech startups, particularly in cross-border transactions and data privacy. This highlights the complexity of navigating Fintech regulations, which vary significantly across jurisdictions (Custers and Overwater 2019; Zhu and Zhou 2016). Understanding these diverse legal stances is crucial for CF platforms that utilize blockchain because they can significantly impact how such platforms operate internationally. Such platforms must navigate international regulatory landscapes, which can significantly influence their operational strategies and market reach.

Additionally, the evolving regulatory landscape presents a dual-edged sword for CF platforms that use blockchain technologies. Well-defined regulations can legitimize and

foster trust in blockchain applications, making them attractive to potential users and investors. However, stringent or unclear regulations may stifle innovation and deter the adoption of innovative solutions in the CF space. To navigate these challenges effectively, CF platforms must engage in proactive legal and regulatory analyses. This involves adherence to current laws and active participation in dialogue with regulatory bodies (Gorkhali and Chowdhury 2022). Thus, they can advocate regulations that support technological advancement while protecting stakeholders (Islam et al. 2021; Yasar 2021). Understanding these regulations can help platforms anticipate changes and adapt their operations accordingly, ensuring compliance and competitive advantages. Overall, the legal and regulatory environment for blockchain in CF is a dynamic arena that requires continuous attention. Stakeholders must remain vigilant and informed to harness the benefits of blockchain technology while mitigating legal risks and navigating regulatory complexities.

Further, Fintech ecosystems have reshaped the industrial landscape and fostered innovation. Several studies have examined the components and actors of fintech ecosystems, such as startups, investors, regulators, and traditional financial institutions, and analyzed their interactions and dynamics (Hua et al. 2019; Milian et al. 2019; Sangwan et al. 2020; Sun et al. 2022). The findings suggest that the success of Fintech startups depends on various factors, including access to funding, talent, partnerships, and favorable regulatory environments. The regulatory landscape is also evolving rapidly, as highlighted by Barbereau and Bodó (2023) and Dinçkol et al. (2023). These authors discuss emerging regulations in response to Fintech innovations, such as open banking standards and the regulation of digital wallets and payment systems. The dynamic nature of these regulations presents both opportunities and challenges for Fintech companies, requiring them to be agile and well informed about legal changes (Dapp et al. 2015).

The use of artificial intelligence and machine learning in Fintech has also been explored, with a focus on the opportunities and challenges in financial applications. The integration of these technologies further intersects with legal and regulatory considerations, particularly in terms of data protection, algorithmic transparency, and the ethical use of AI in financial decision making (Giudici 2018).

CF platforms' use of blockchain technology to improve transactional efficiency, authenticity, and security was the main focus of the third cluster. Several scholars have investigated how blockchain-based CF can overcome conventional financing issues and promote social value creation (Nguyen et al. 2021). Similarly, the use of smart contracts to facilitate secure and automatic financial transactions on CF platforms has been the subject of recurrent research. For example, Yadav and Sarasvathi (2020) proposed a method for CF using blockchain technology and smart contracts to provide investors with a decentralized, secure, and confidential way to support projects and manage their invested funds. Mas et al. (2020) examined the use of blockchain technology and smart contracts to support sustainable business models and found that smart contracts can lower transaction costs, increase social trust, and encourage social-proof behavior, sustaining the development of new sustainable business models. Furthermore, CF platforms that use blockchain technology can boost social value creation and provide financial support for public welfare projects such as those relating to tertiary education and ethical reforms (Nguyen et al. 2021). Another significant area of research in this cluster explores

how blockchain-based CF affects traditional fundraising methods, specifically focusing on comparing blockchain-based conventional models (F. Hartmann et al. 2019). Some studies have also examined the factors contributing to the success of blockchain-based CF platforms, including the quality of the CF project, level of community engagement, and ease of use of the technology (e.g., Hartmann et al. 2019). Finally, the challenges and risks associated with blockchain-based CF, such as data breaches, third-party platform risks, and the need for proper guidelines and regulations, are highlighted in the literature.

The fourth cluster covers various aspects of blockchain technology, proposes new frameworks and methods to address related issues and challenges, and highlights its potential benefits of blockchain technology in terms of security, privacy, and trust. Specifically, scholars have examined the challenges faced by developers in creating high-quality smart contracts, such as the lack of effective tools and resources and the difficulty in ensuring code security (Zou et al. 2021). Several studies have described the potential benefits of using blockchain technology to address these issues and enhance the efficiency and transparency of CF. For example, Khatter et al. (2021) suggested the use of blockchain and smart contracts to develop a more transparent, trustworthy, and cost-efficient CF system. Vakili et al. (2018) proposed blockchain technology to develop a new framework for ensuring cyber products that include a sealed-bid auction and the use of tokens to address cyber risks.

The fifth cluster focuses on the potential of blockchain to disrupt traditional financial intermediation and support venture capital CF for creative ventures. O'Dair and Owen (2019) discussed the potential of blockchain to offer alternative entrepreneurial financing via token sales or ICOs for creative ventures in the music industry. Ackermann et al. (2020) argued that blockchain can disrupt conventional financial intermediaries and create new intermediaries that are more transparent and efficient. This is particularly evident in the case of CF and ICOs, where blockchain can provide a more accessible and democratic form of entrepreneurial finance that can bypass traditional gatekeepers, such as venture capitalists and banks (Campino et al. 2021; Gonzalez 2023; Subramanian 2020). Another critical theme that emerged from the cluster analysis was the regulatory challenges and opportunities associated with blockchain technology. For instance, Deng et al. (2018) conduct a comparative analysis of regulatory frameworks for ICOs in developed economies and suggest potential regulatory reform for the current ICO ban in China. Literature on the role of formal institutions and financial regulators in promoting operational excellence and stakeholder engagement in the financial sector further underscores the need for effective governance and accountability mechanisms in the Fintech industry.

The final cluster revealed a common interest in examining the potential of blockchain to improve financial systems, governance, and social development. For example, Block et al. (2021) compared CF and ICOs as important future entrepreneurial finance market segments, whereas Seyedsayamdost and Vanderwal (2020) investigated the use of blockchain in development and humanitarian aid. The literature in this cluster also highlights the limitations and challenges associated with blockchain, including centralizing tendencies and barriers to technology adoption (e.g., ethics). For example, a study on micro-finance institutions (MFIs) identified the need to use technology properly to minimize

operational and technical problems facing the industry (Jeyasheela Rakkini and Geetha 2021). Mukkamala et al. (2019) explore the application of blockchain technology to address the challenges encountered by social businesses, which are business models for investment in social causes. The authors highlight the potential of blockchain in enhancing trust, transparency, and auditability in social business activities and identify the challenges related to creating a native cryptocurrency for social causes and barriers to infrastructure and technology adoption.

Keyword co-occurrence analysis

When using CiteSpace to perform keyword co-occurrence analysis, scholars can switch between a time-zone view and a timeline view to better grasp and discover the dynamics of a study topic. A visual analysis that considers time is beneficial for spotting trends and tracking the development of a research field. As certain terms are interchangeable, the synonyms were combined in the initial data package to form a file called “Citespace. aka” before CiteSpace was used. To simplify things, terms such as “initial coin offering,” “initial coin offerings,” and “initial coin offering (ico)” were all rolled into one, while terms such as “small and medium enterprises,” “small and medium-sized enterprises,” “SMEs,” and “SME” were merged into “SME”. Figure 5 depicts a time-zone view based on frequently recurring terms that can be used to track the history of these terms and how they are related. The placement of each node, which represents a different term, was determined by the year in which the term first appeared. The larger the node, the more often the two terms have occurred together since their introduction. As an example, from 2015 to 2023 (up to March), the keyword “blockchain” occurred 432 times in conjunction with other keywords, but “entrepreneurial finance,” which arrived later, appeared only 52 times from 2020 to 2023.

Blockchain, crowdfunding, smart contracts, ico, fintech, cryptocurrency, Ethereum, innovation, entrepreneurial finance, and p2p lending are among the top 10 most often co-cited by scholars, as shown in Fig. 5. Financial inclusion, bitcoin, token sale, token

Fig. 5 Time zone view based on keyword clustering

Table 4 Most relevant keywords based on co-occurrence

Num	Keyword	CC	Num	Keyword	CC
1	Blockchain	432	21	P2P	28
2	Crowdfunding	280	22	Tokens	28
3	Smart contracts	181	23	Financial services	27
4	ICO	156	24	Signaling	24
5	Fintech	150	25	AI	23
6	Cryptocurrency	137	26	Crypto-assets	23
7	Ethereum	121	27	Fundraising	23
8	Innovation	55	28	Finance	21
9	Entrepreneurial finance	52	29	Financial sector	21
10	P2P lending	52	30	Technology	21
11	Financial inclusion	39	31	Banking	20
12	Bitcoin	38	32	Lending	19
13	Token sale	37	33	Tokenization	19
14	Token offering	33	34	Bank	16
15	Venture capital	33	35	Microfinance	16
16	Solidity	32	36	RegTech	16
17	DLTs	31	37	SMEs	14
18	STOs	31	38	Big data	13
19	DApps	29	39	Charity	13
20	Moral hazard	29	40	Crowdfunding	13

Fig. 6 Timeline view based on keywords

offering, venture capital, solidity, and distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) are additional popular terms. Keywords such as privacy, charity, Islamic fintech, machine learning, and non-fungible tokens (nft) have garnered much interest in recent studies. These terms refer to trending discussions and new developments. Table 4 provides additional information on these terms.

Timeline views, contrary to time-zone views, are presented in a cluster form. Figure 6 depicts the timeline view presented in this study, categorizing the findings of the co-word analysis into the following seven clusters: Cluster 0 (blockchain), Cluster 1 (smart contracts), Cluster 2 (fundraising campaigns), Cluster 3 (public relations), Cluster 4 (loan platforms), Cluster 5 (sustainable entrepreneurship), and Cluster 6

Table 5 Keyword clustering details

ClusterID	Cluster label	Size	Keywords	Timespan
0	Blockchain	17	Blockchain; crowdfunding; fintech; cryptocurrency; P2P lending; innovation; financial inclusion; AI; financial service; financial regulation; technology; loan; platform; bank; payment; fundraiser; defi	2015–2022
1	Smart contracts	14	Smart contract; ethereum; DApp; solidity; fundraising; SME; donation; transparency; consensus; sidechain; charity; NFT; decentralized; campaign	2015–2022
2	Fundraising campaigns	9	Bitcoin; DLT; token sale; token offering; financial sector; STO; consensus algorithm; crypto-asset; distributed ledger	2015–2021
3	Public relations	10	ICO; token; ECF; taxonomy; bibliometric; collaboration; transaction management; topic modeling; design science; crowdinvesting	2016–2021
4	Loan platforms	7	P2P; finance; lending; mobile payment; privacy; social capital; zero-knowledge proof	2018–2022
5	Sustainable entrepreneurship	5	Entrepreneurial finance; big data; RegTech; blockchain-based crowdfunding; machine learning	2019–2022
6	Islamic Fintech	3	Islamic fintech; challenge; Islamic finance	2021–2023

(Islamic fintech). The yellow line shows the lifespan of each cluster, and Table 5 provides more detailed information on the seven clusters.

Cluster #0, aptly labeled “blockchain,” is the most prominent, spanning from 2015 to 2022. This cluster comprises diverse keywords including blockchain, crowdfunding, fintech, cryptocurrency, P2P lending, innovation, and financial inclusion. The high frequency of blockchain as a primary keyword within this cluster indicates the growing importance of the technology in the CF landscape (Bogusz et al. 2020b; Nguyen et al. 2021). This is further evidenced by the presence of related keywords such as cryptocurrency and defi (decentralized finance), which suggests that blockchain is being used as a CF platform and a means to support decentralized finance applications (Hartmann et al. 2019). Adarsh et al. (2023) argue that these approaches have significant benefits over traditional centralized financial systems and can operate with greater transparency without requiring escrow services or central clearinghouses. Hartmann and Hasan (2022) noted that blockchain can support DeFi applications through its decentralized and transparent nature, enabling DeFi applications to operate efficiently.

Moreover, the inclusion of fintech and financial services in the cluster indicates the potential for blockchain technology to revolutionize traditional financial services, with CF being just one example (Bogusz et al. 2020a; Zhu and Zhou 2016). Several studies have discussed the concepts of financial inclusion and P2P lending (Alshater et al. 2023; Bhatt et al. 2022; Hughes 2021), highlighting the role of blockchain-based CF in promoting financial inclusion, particularly in developing countries (Mbodji et al. 2020; Zhu and Zhou 2016). The emergence of the keyword AI suggests that this technology can be increasingly used in the CF industry, potentially leading to more efficient and effective fundraising campaigns (Bhatt et al. 2022). As such, AI can automate some aspects of the CF process, including identifying potential

backers, targeting them through personalized messaging, and analyzing campaign performance (Cai 2018). This increased automation can help reduce human errors and increase the accuracy of CF campaigns. Finally, the keywords financial regulation and bank highlight the significance of regulatory frameworks in the largely unregulated blockchain-based CF industry in many countries. Overall, the first cluster sheds light on the complex and ever-changing CF landscape and the potential of blockchain to disrupt conventional financial services and advance financial inclusion.

The second cluster is labeled “smart contracts” and presents an intriguing dimension of the evolving intersection between CF and blockchain research. Conceptually, smart contracts are autonomous contracts in which contractual provisions are encoded directly into a computer code, allowing them to execute automatically (Dal Mas et al. 2020). These contracts are implemented on blockchain systems in which they are automatically executed if certain criteria are fulfilled, eliminating the need for middlemen (Yadav and Sarasvathi 2020). Smart contracts guarantee transparency, security, and immutability in transactions, substantially reducing the likelihood of fraud and mistakes (Annenkov et al. 2020).

The confluence of these keywords suggests a tapestry of interrelated themes that warrants further exploration to better understand the implications and potential applications of blockchain in the CF domain. For several reasons, smart contracts are relevant in the context of CF. First, they can automate numerous phases of the CF process, from fundraising to fund distribution (Shelke et al. 2022). This automated process minimizes the administrative burden and guarantees that money is disbursed only upon the achievement of predetermined project milestones or the fulfillment of specified requirements (Aggarwal and Kumar 2021). For example, a smart contract may be coded to disburse funding for a project only after a certain level of capital has been obtained, boosting trust and ensuring accountability (Dal Mas et al. 2020). Smart contracts provide transparency and immutability by securely documenting all transactions in a blockchain and creating a comprehensive and unchangeable record of all events. The openness of financial transactions allows investors to validate the movement of money and comply with project requirements in real-time, fostering confidence (Mas and Chuen 2015). The security measures of blockchain technology also safeguard against unauthorized modifications and cyberattacks, which are essential for preserving the integrity of CF systems (Jeyasheela Rakkini and Geetha 2021). Additionally, smart contracts enable decentralized transactions, diminishing the need for conventional financial intermediaries, such as banks or payment processors. Decentralization may reduce transaction costs and improve the inclusiveness of CF by enabling numerous participants, especially those in places with underdeveloped financial infrastructures (Mhlanga 2023; Rejeb et al. 2024b). Furthermore, smart contracts can adhere to regulatory standards by including compliance rules directly in the code. This feature guarantees that CF campaigns comply with legal regulations in many countries, streamlining international CF projects, and safeguarding investors from legal ambiguities (Collomb et al. 2019).

Ethereum is a renowned blockchain platform that acts as the foundational framework for many decentralized apps (DApps), with Solidity as its main programming language. The frequent occurrence of these concepts highlights the importance of Ethereum and its ecosystems in facilitating blockchain-based CF solutions. Ethereum’s resilient and

adaptable architecture allows developers to design intricate smart contracts and DApps customized to the distinct requirements of CF projects (Panda 2020). For example, DApps built on the Ethereum blockchain may provide novel functionalities, such as tokenized equity (Roth et al. 2021), where supporters obtain digital tokens that reflect their ownership in a project. Further, reputation systems can be implemented to evaluate the trustworthiness of CF campaigns and their creators based on their previous track records (Basu et al. 2022). These developments have improved the functioning of CF platforms and have provided new prospects for investor participation and project financing. In summary, the incorporation of smart contracts into CF systems, namely Ethereum, signifies a revolutionary advancement in the digital finance domain. Smart contracts effectively address the difficulties that the CF industry now encounters by automating operations, improving security and transparency, decentralizing transactions, and assuring compliance with regulations. Further exploration of these themes is essential to fully understand their potential and to drive innovation in the CF sector.

The second cluster encompassed keywords such as fundraising, SMEs, donation, transparency, consensus, side chain, and charity. These keywords collectively allude to numerous smart contract use cases in the CF landscape, including peer-to-peer fundraising for small and medium enterprises (SMEs), transparent donation platforms for charitable causes, and non-fungible tokens (NFT) campaigns that capitalize on the digital scarcity of unique assets (Basu et al. 2022). According to several studies (e.g., Chawla 2020), transparency and consensus are central to the value of blockchain-based CF platforms. For instance, Sirisawat et al. (2022) argue that the immutability and public accessibility of transaction records engender a higher degree of accountability and trustworthiness because donors and investors can independently verify the legitimacy of CF campaigns and the utilization of their contributions. Hoffmann (2021) notes that the decentralized nature of blockchain obviates the need for intermediaries, reducing transaction costs and empowering participants to have greater control over their investments. Another highly frequent keyword in the cluster is “sidechains,” which represent auxiliary blockchain networks operating in parallel to the main chain. These secondary blockchain networks can expand the possibilities for tailored CF solutions. By allowing for customizable consensus mechanisms and enhanced scalability, side chains can accommodate the specific requirements of CF campaigns and foster innovation in this field.

Fundraising campaigns represent the focus of the third cluster, providing insights into the use of blockchain technology and digital assets in the financial sector. This cluster encapsulates various ideas that exemplify the disruptive power of blockchain-based fundraising initiatives and their far-reaching consequences in the financial services industry. Bitcoin, DLT, token sale, token offering, STO (security token offering), and consensus algorithms are some of the most widespread keywords in the cluster. These terms collectively represent the various innovative methods and mechanisms that employ blockchain technology and digital assets, including digital currencies, to achieve fundraising objectives.

While blockchain technology underpins the creation and operation of digital currencies, such as Bitcoin, its application in CF showcases distinct uses and challenges. Bitcoin, as the first decentralized digital currency, led to the emergence of numerous other cryptocurrencies and opened new avenues for blockchain applications beyond

digital currencies (Hoffmann 2021). In the context of CF, blockchain offers unique advantages, such as enhanced security, transparency, and the ability to create and exchange digital assets such as tokens. These tokens, which can be utility or security, facilitate fundraising by representing the values or rights within a project. Nonetheless, the use of blockchain in CF differs significantly from its use in digital currencies. While digital currencies primarily focus on creating an alternative to traditional financial systems, blockchain in CF emphasizes democratizing access to capital and improving the efficiency and trustworthiness of the fundraising processes. Digital currencies face challenges such as price volatility and regulatory scrutiny (Rejeb et al. 2021c), whereas blockchain in CF must address issues related to platform governance, investor protection, and the legal status of tokens.

Token sales and offerings are two new fundraising tools enabled by blockchain. Conceptually, token sales and offers encompass various fundraising mechanisms, including ICOs, STOs, and Initial Exchange Offerings (IEOs) (Rrustemi and Tuchschnid 2020). These mechanisms democratize access to funding by connecting investors to innovative projects and ventures through the insurance of digital tokens (Collomb et al. 2019). Specifically, STOs represent a regulated variant of token offerings that adhere to securities regulations and offer investors legal protection and rights (Mattke et al. 2021). As indicated by its inclusion in the cluster, the financial sector benefits significantly from integrating DLT with digital assets (Kotsialou et al. 2018). Scholars argue that financial institutions can streamline operations, enhance efficiency, and reduce the costs associated with traditional fundraising campaigns by harnessing the power of the consensus of algorithms.

The fourth cluster, labeled “public relation”, delves into the multifaceted nature of fundraising mechanisms and methodologies employed in the analysis and exploration of CF and blockchain research. The keywords in this cluster include ICO, token, ECF, taxonomy, bibliometric, collaboration, and transaction management. These terms collectively represent the convergence of fundraising instruments (Collomb et al. 2019), research methodologies, and collaborative approaches to blockchain-based CF activities. In this cluster, ICOs and tokens signify the adoption of digital assets in fundraising campaigns, enabling CF projects to raise capital by issuing digital tokens to investors (Chen 2018). Equity CF represents another form of decentralized fundraising that enables individual investors to acquire equity shares in early stage companies, further democratizing the investment landscape (Guggenberger et al. 2023).

The inclusion of keyword taxonomy and bibliometric analysis indicates the use of these methodological approaches to organize, categorize, and quantify research contributions in the realm of blockchain and CF systematically. These approaches facilitate the identification of knowledge gaps and emerging trends, allowing researchers to refine their understanding of the evolving landscape and foster interdisciplinary collaboration (Bargoni et al. 2022a, b). Similarly, collaboration and transaction management underscore the importance of relationships and efficient processes in the realm of blockchain-based CF. Decentralized platforms can facilitate seamless coordination among stakeholders, ensuring trust and reducing the transaction costs associated with fundraising campaigns. Finally, the keyword crowdinvesting highlights the idea that fundraising initiatives are about raising money and empowering individual

investors to participate in the growth and success of innovative ventures (Gruzina et al. 2016).

The fifth cluster, labeled “loan platforms,” explores the potential of decentralized and peer-to-peer (P2P) lending solutions enabled by blockchain technology. This cluster includes several studies that emphasize the convergence of innovative financial services, privacy-enhancing mechanisms, and social capital, which are crucial for reshaping the lending landscape (Giudici 2018). The high frequency of the keywords P2P, finance, and lending indicates the growing significance of decentralized loan platforms that leverage blockchain technology to facilitate direct transactions between borrowers and lenders (Bhatia and Kiran 2017). Gonzalez (2020) contends that these platforms represent a paradigm shift in the financial services industry because they reduce reliance on traditional intermediaries, such as banks and other financial institutions. This reduces transaction costs and increases credit accessibility for a broader range of borrowers. Furthermore, the concept of mobile payments was studied in this cluster, reflecting the seamless integration of loan platforms with a broader digital payment ecosystem. The ubiquity of mobile devices and the rapid growth of digital payment solutions have enabled innovative lending services to reach a wider audience, democratizing access to financial resources (Chen 2018).

By capitalizing on the power of mobile technology, P2P loan platforms can cater to the needs of unbanked and underbanked populations (Alshater et al. 2022) and foster financial inclusion (Hughes 2021). The terms’ privacy and zero-knowledge proof highlight the need to maintain user privacy and protect data on decentralized loan platforms. In cryptography, zero-knowledge proofs are used to establish the validity of statements without disclosing any associated private data. Integrating such privacy-preserving mechanisms within P2P lending platforms ensures that sensitive financial data remain confidential, while enabling secure and transparent transactions (Kim and Hong 2017). Further, the cluster contains the term social capital, which refers to the crucial role of trust, reputation, and relationship building in the efficacy of P2P loan platforms (Hartmann and Hasan 2022). In decentralized lending models, social capital is often utilized to evaluate creditworthiness and mitigate risk because conventional credit scoring methods may not suffice or be relevant in such scenarios. Through the use of reputation systems and social networks, P2P lending platforms can promote trust and confidence among participants, allowing for better-informed decision-making and the facilitation of mutually beneficial transactions (Mahajan and Srivastava 2019).

The sixth and seventh clusters of keyword co-occurrences highlighted the potential of financial innovation to drive sustainable development and cater to the specific needs of diverse communities. These clusters prioritize sustainable entrepreneurship, which includes important concepts such as entrepreneurial finance, big data, RegTech, blockchain-based CE, and machine learning. This subject is crucial in strengthening sustainable ventures by providing them with the required funding and facilitating data-driven decision making (Nguyen et al. 2021; Polas et al. 2022).

Sustainable entrepreneurship entails the establishment and administration of enterprises that strive for economic viability while simultaneously prioritizing environmental and social objectives (Tenner and Hörisch 2021). An all-encompassing strategy is crucial for tackling worldwide concerns, such as climate change, resource

depletion, and social and economic inequality. Financial innovation is crucial for promoting sustainable entrepreneurship, as it provides novel means and techniques for acquiring funds, mitigating risks, and improving operational effectiveness (Yacoub et al. 2022). Blockchain-based CF is an innovation that transforms the process of seeking financing from sustainable companies. CF platforms use the blockchain technology to enhance transaction transparency and security. Transparency fosters confidence among investors by allowing them to monitor the allocation of money and verify that the projects they endorse align with their sustainability objectives (Rizwan and Mustafa 2022). Furthermore, the decentralized structure of blockchain technology decreases dependence on conventional financial intermediaries, resulting in reduced expenses and enhanced funding availability for businesses in marginalized groups (Giudici 2018).

Big data is a crucial element of sustainable entrepreneurship. The enormous amount of data produced in the contemporary digital economy can be used to acquire a more profound understanding of market trends, customer behaviors, and investment prospects (Cappa 2022). Big data analytics can be used to identify the most influential areas of investment and forecast the prospective consequences of different tactics for sustainable businesses. The use of data-driven methods allows for well-informed decision-making, which is essential for the success and expansion of sustainable enterprises. Entrepreneurs can improve their awareness of the risks and possibilities linked to their businesses by scrutinizing patterns and trends. This enables them to continually adapt and innovate (Bayram et al. 2022).

RegTech, which means regulatory technology, aids sustainable entrepreneurship by streamlining adherence to regulatory obligations. This is especially crucial for sustainable ventures, which often operate in heavily regulated industries such as renewable energy, waste management, and social enterprises. RegTech solutions use cutting-edge technologies, such as AI and blockchain, to streamline compliance procedures, alleviate administrative complexities, and guarantee adherence to applicable regulations and benchmarks (Collomb et al. 2019). This reduces risk and enables entrepreneurs to concentrate more on their core activities and innovation (Bayram et al. 2022). Finally, machine learning increases sustainable business by facilitating predictive analytics and automation (Gupta et al. 2023). Machine learning algorithms can efficiently scan extensive information to discern patterns and forecast future trends, assisting entrepreneurs in making proactive choices. For example, machine learning can be used to forecast demand for sustainable products, optimize supply chains, and enhance customer engagement through personalized marketing. This technology empowers sustainable ventures to operate more efficiently and effectively, maximizing their positive impacts on society and the environment (Giudici 2018).

The final cluster comprised keywords such as Islamic fintech, challenges, and Islamic finance, highlighting the growing prominence of technology-driven financial solutions that adhere to Islamic principles (Alshater et al. 2022; Ascarya and Sakti 2022; Baber 2020c). However, this sector faces challenges in regulatory compliance, risk management, and technology adoption (Rabbani et al. 2020). Blockchain offers unique benefits in terms of secure and transparent transactions that comply with Islamic financial principles (Baber 2020b). Conversely, big data and machine learning

can help analyze financial patterns and risks, although their use must be carefully balanced with ethical and legal considerations in Islamic finance (Alshater et al. 2022).

Discussion and future research directions

Discussion

Despite the significance of blockchain and CF in Fintech development, no study has provided a comprehensive overview of the research on the intersection of these topics. This study examined the current state of research on blockchain-based CF by conducting a systematic literature review using bibliometric methods. While this approach is relatively new to the Fintech field, this study is the first to address the research questions from the perspective of blockchain-based CF. A total of 219 publications were collected from Scopus, adhering to the systematic review guidelines. To perform a bibliometric analysis, the authors analyzed the descriptive statistics of the selected publications, article co-citations, and keyword co-occurrences. In the co-citation and keyword co-occurrence analysis section, three visualization views were implemented with the support of CiteSpace: cluster, time zone, and timeline views. Analyzing these visualizations enables us to detect the pivotal points and dynamics of blockchain-based CF research.

This study uses descriptive statistics to recognize the progression of academic output, productive countries and academic institutions, top sources, and influential publications in CF and blockchain research. Overall, the analysis shows an increase in annual publications from 2015 to 2023 (up to March), with a surge occurring after 2018. This suggests a significant boost in interest and research activity in the CF and blockchain fields in recent years. This may be due to various factors such as advancements in technology (Nguyen et al. 2021), increased awareness, and the realization of the potential benefits of CF and blockchain in various industries and applications. As blockchain continues to evolve, scholars will likely explore its various aspects and implications in greater detail.

The geographic distribution of research on blockchain technology and CF reveals stark disparities, with countries such as India and the United States leading in publications, reflecting their advanced research infrastructure and supportive ecosystems. Conversely, contributions from African countries, such as Tunisia, Ghana, Morocco, Nigeria, Senegal, and South Africa, were significantly lower. This highlights the gaps in resources and engagement between these regions. This disparity influences the volume and focus of research topics, with leading nations exploring the advanced integration of blockchain, and emerging regions addressing more foundational challenges. Therefore, addressing these disparities is crucial for a balanced global development of blockchain and CF technologies to ensure that innovations are inclusive and universally beneficial. Singapore Management University, the University of California, and the University of Pennsylvania were the most productive institutions. This information could be valuable for policymakers and industry players seeking to understand the global landscape of CF and blockchain technology research and identify new research collaboration and investment areas. The most influential publications on CF and blockchain research were those of Gomber et al. (2018), Chen (2018) and Thakor (2020). These works are considered groundbreaking because they make critical contributions to the understanding of the impact of emerging technologies on financial services and the broader socioeconomic landscape, providing valuable insights for scholars, practitioners, and policymakers.

Co-citation network analysis reveals diverse research themes that explore various aspects of CF and blockchain technology. The most important cluster focuses on the role of ICOs in enabling new forms of entrepreneurial finance, highlighting the importance of understanding the factors contributing to successful ICOs and the potential implications of blockchain-based CF for the financial industry. The prominence of the ICO cluster in the co-citation network reflects the growing interest in blockchain-based fundraising mechanisms and their potential impact on the financial industry. Understanding the factors that contribute to successful ICOs can help entrepreneurs and investors make informed decisions, and the potential implications of blockchain-based CF in the financial industry emphasize the need for further research in this area. The second cluster highlights the significant impact of Fintech on the financial industry, specifically the disruptive potential of blockchain technology and its smart contract features. The use of blockchain technology in P2P lending and CF has already shown potential benefits such as transparency, security, and efficiency (Gonzalez 2023). Nonetheless, the integration of blockchain technology into other financial services and the emergence of new Fintech applications could disrupt traditional financial intermediation systems (Sun et al. 2022). One interesting area of study within this cluster is fintech ecosystems and the different actors involved, including startups, investors, regulators, and traditional financial institutions.

A keyword co-occurrence analysis offers a comprehensive view of the CF and blockchain research landscape, revealing the most significant research themes and their potential implications. The first cluster highlights the growing importance of blockchain technology in CF. Blockchain-based CF solutions can transform traditional financial services and promote financial inclusion. Nevertheless, the absence of a regulatory framework poses significant challenges to the development of blockchain-based CF platforms. The second cluster highlights the potential of blockchain and smart contracts to enable transparent, secure, and decentralized transactions. The importance of Ethereum in facilitating blockchain-based CF solutions has also been emphasized. Transparent and consensus mechanisms have been identified as central to the value of blockchain-based CF platforms, promoting accountability and trustworthiness. The cluster also emphasizes the importance of side chains in fostering innovation. The third cluster shows the disruptive power of blockchain-based fundraising initiatives and their potential to revolutionize traditional fundraising methods. Token sales and offerings democratize access to funding by connecting investors to innovative projects and ventures through digital tokens. The financial sector can significantly benefit from integrating DLT and digital assets, reducing the costs associated with traditional fundraising campaigns. The remaining clusters of analysis focused on fundraising instruments, loan platforms, sustainable entrepreneurship, and Islamic Fintech.

Future research directions

Based on the findings of the bibliometric analysis, several future research directions are proposed.

- Investigate the long-term effects of ICOs and blockchain-based CF on traditional financing methods and financial intermediaries. As ICOs and blockchain-based CF

continue to grow, it is crucial to understand how these novel financing methods impact traditional financing methods, such as venture capital, angel investing, and bank loans.

- Explore the role of regulations in the development and adoption of blockchain-based CF platforms. As regulatory frameworks are essential for promoting trust and stability in financial markets, understanding the best practices for creating effective regulations that encourage innovation while mitigating risks is crucial.
- Analyze the potential of blockchain technology in other financial services beyond P2P lending and CF. The integration of blockchain technology in areas such as insurance, remittances, and asset management could further disrupt the financial industry and provide additional benefits, such as enhanced transparency and reduced costs.
- Examine the potential of blockchain-based CF platforms to foster financial inclusion and promote social impact. This could involve researching the effectiveness of these platforms in supporting underfunded and underserved segments of society, such as female entrepreneurs, minority-owned businesses, and social enterprises.
- Investigate the use of alternative consensus mechanisms and side chains in blockchain-based CF platforms. As the current research highlights the importance of consensus mechanisms in promoting trust and accountability, future research could explore alternative mechanisms such as proof-of-stake, delegated proof-of-stake, and practical Byzantine fault tolerance, as well as the potential of side chains to foster innovation in blockchain-based CF platforms.
- Assess the potential of blockchain technology in Islamic Fintech and ethical financing. Blockchain technology could provide an innovative solution for promoting transparency, accountability, and compliance with Islamic finance principles. Future research could explore the opportunities and challenges associated with implementing blockchain solutions in this context.
- Investigate the role of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in enhancing blockchain-based CF platforms. Integrating AI and ML techniques could help streamline various aspects of CF platforms, such as risk assessment, investor matching, and fraud detection. Future research could focus on identifying the most effective approaches to harness these technologies in the CF and blockchain space.

Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the research landscape at the intersection of blockchain technology and CF through a systematic literature review using bibliometric methods. The findings reveal an increase in research publications from 2015 to 2023, with a notable surge after 2018, indicating growing interest and activity in blockchain-based CF. Leading countries in research output include India and the United States, whereas African nations show significantly fewer contributions, highlighting geographic disparities. Notable academic institutions such as Singapore Management University and the University of California are leading in productivity, and influential publications by authors such as Gomber et al. (2018) and Chen (2018) have significantly shaped the understanding of blockchain and CF. Moreover, the key research themes identified include the role of ICOs in entrepreneurial finance, emphasizing the

importance of understanding the factors contributing to successful ICOs; the disruptive impact of Fintech, particularly blockchain technology and smart contracts, on traditional financial services; and the potential of blockchain and smart contracts to enable transparent, secure, and decentralized transactions, with Ethereum playing a significant role. These findings align with the objectives of mapping the research landscape, identifying key themes, and understanding the global distribution of research efforts in blockchain-based CF. Future research should address geographic disparities and explore regulatory frameworks to foster inclusive and innovative developments in the CF and blockchain fields.

This study has multifaceted theoretical implications. First, by identifying research clusters, this study helps organize and categorize the existing knowledge in the field, making it more accessible and easier for researchers and academics to understand. The identification of these clusters also revealed areas of convergence and divergence within the research community, providing a framework for future theoretical discussions and investigations. Second, developing a holistic understanding of blockchain-based CF will contribute to a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of this emerging field. This, in turn, can inform the development of new theories, models, and frameworks that can better explain the complexities and dynamics of blockchain-based CF. For example, researchers might explore how blockchain technology can facilitate trust and transparency in CF or how smart contracts can be utilized to create more efficient and secure funding mechanisms.

The practical implications of this study are as follows. The insights provided can help entrepreneurs and startups better understand the factors that contribute to successful ICOs, allowing them to design and implement more effective fundraising strategies. This can lead to increased chances of attracting funding and fostering innovation within organizations. For investors, the practical implications involve a deeper understanding of the blockchain-based CF landscape, enabling them to make informed decisions when evaluating investment opportunities. This can lead to a more efficient capital allocation and potentially higher returns on investment. For practitioners, these insights are crucial for developing and refining blockchain-based CF platforms to ensure that they meet the needs of fundraisers and investors. Finally, this study offers guidance for policymakers and regulators on the potential implications of blockchain-based CF in the financial industry. This can inform the development of appropriate regulatory frameworks and policies that strike a balance between fostering innovation and ensuring stability and security in financial systems. By understanding the potential benefits and risks associated with blockchain-based CF, policymakers can create a supportive environment for the growth and adoption of novel fundraising mechanisms, ultimately promoting financial inclusion and economic growth.

Although this study offers significant insights into the blockchain domain, it has a few methodological limitations. Bibliometric analysis, primarily sourced from Scopus, may not have captured the entire spectrum of relevant literature, especially given the dynamic and rapidly evolving nature of blockchain technology and related areas such as equity CF and ICOs. Consequently, some pertinent studies, particularly those from sources other than Scopus, or those published after March 2023, may not have been included. Additionally, reliance on a single database could introduce bias towards certain types of publications

or research communities, potentially overlooking valuable insights from less-represented sources.

Another limitation is the scope of the literature review. The focus was predominantly on academic and peer-reviewed articles, possibly omitting relevant insights from industry reports, whitepapers, and other gray literature, which can be particularly informative in rapidly advancing fields such as blockchain and Fintech. Future research could address these limitations by employing a more expansive approach to literature collection, incorporating multiple databases, and including a broader range of publications. Furthermore, updating the review period to include more recent publications ensures a more comprehensive capture of the latest developments and trends in the field.

Additionally, our exclusive use of bibliometric analysis may have overlooked deeper thematic and developmental trends in the literature. Methods such as topic modeling and main path analysis offer additional insight into the evolution of themes and the progression of research fronts in blockchain and CF. Topic modeling allows us to uncover latent topics and track their emergence and decline over time, providing a dynamic view of a field's intellectual structure (Rejeb et al. 2024a, b, c, d, e; Zrelli et al. 2024). Nonetheless, main path analysis could identify the most impactful studies, trace the pathways of knowledge flow, and highlight key contributions and their interconnections (Rejeb et al. 2023a; Yu et al. 2022). Incorporating these methodologies in future research could provide a more holistic and nuanced understanding of this domain.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
CF	Crowdfunding
DApps	Decentralized applications
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
FinTech	Financial Technology
IEO	Initial exchange offerings
ICO	Initial coin offerings
IPO	Initial public offerings
LLR	Log-likelihood ratio
MFI	Microfinance institutions
NFT	Non-fungible tokens
P2P	Peer-to-peer
SME	Small and medium enterprises
STO	Security token offerings

Author contributions

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Data are available upon request.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Received: 25 September 2023 Accepted: 11 November 2024

Published online: 05 January 2025

References

- Abdollahi A, Rejeb K, Rejeb A, Mostafa MM, Zailani S (2021) Wireless sensor networks in agriculture: insights from bibliometric analysis. *Sustainability* 13(21):12011. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132112011>
- Ackermann E, Bock C, Bürger R (2020) Democratizing entrepreneurial finance: the impact of crowdfunding and initial coin offerings (ICOs). *FGF Stud Small Bus Entrep*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-17612-9_11
- Adarsh S, Anoop VS, Asharaf S (2023) Distributed consensus mechanism with novelty classification using proof of immune algorithm. *Lect Notes Netw Syst* 471:173–183. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-2535-1_13
- Aggarwal S, Kumar N (2021) Blockchain 2.0: smart contracts. In: Aggarwal S, Kumar N, Raj P (eds) *Advances in computers*, vol 121. Elsevier, pp 301–322
- AllahRakha N (2023) Legal challenges for international fintech startups. *Int J Law Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.59022/ijlp.148>
- Alshater MM, Saba I, Supriani I, Rabbani MR (2022) Fintech in Islamic finance literature: a review. *Heliyon*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10385>
- Alshater MM, Joshipura M, Khoury RE, Nasrallah N (2023) Initial coin offerings: a hybrid empirical review. *Small Bus Econ*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-022-00726-2>
- Annenkov D, Botsch Nielsen J, Spitters B (2020) ConCert: a smart contract certification framework in Coq. In: CPP 2020—proceedings of the 9th ACM SIGPLAN international conference on certified programs and proofs, co-located with POPL 2020, pp 215–228. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3372885.3373829>
- Arefjevs I, Spilbergs A, Natrins A, Verdenhofs A, Mavlutova I, Volkova T (2020) Financial sector evolution and competencies development in the context of information and communication technologies. *Res Rural Dev* 35:260–267. <https://doi.org/10.22616/rrd.26.2020.038>
- Asaduzzaman M, Hasib F, Hafiz ZB (2020) Towards using blockchain technology for microcredit industry in Bangladesh. In: ICCIT 2020—23rd international conference on computer and information technology, proceedings. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIT51783.2020.9392730>
- Ascarya A, Sakti A (2022) Designing micro-fintech models for Islamic micro financial institutions in Indonesia. *Int J Islam Middle East Finance Manag* 15(2):236–254. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMEFM-05-2020-0233>
- Azevedo P, Gomes J, Romão M (2023) Supply chain traceability using blockchain. *Oper Manag Res* 16(3):1359–1381. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12063-023-00359-y>
- Baber H (2019) Blockchain-based crowdfunding: a ‘pay-it forward’ model of WHIRL. *Int J Recent Technol Eng (IJRTE)* 8(3):2277–3878
- Baber H (2020a) Blockchain-based crowdfunding. In: da Rosa Righi R, Alberti AM, Singh M (eds) *Blockchain technology for industry 4.0: secure, decentralized, distributed and trusted industry environment*. Springer, pp 117–130. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1137-0_6
- Baber H (2020b) Crowdfunding framework in Islamic finance. In: *Handbook of research on theory and practice of global Islamic finance*, pp 307–320. IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-0218-1.ch017>
- Baber H (2020c) FinTech, crowdfunding and customer retention in Islamic banks. *Vision* 24(3):260–268. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972262919869765>
- Baber H, Fanea-Ivanovici M (2022) Fifteen years of crowdfunding—a bibliometric analysis. *Technol Anal Strat Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2022.2089548>
- Barbareau T, Bodó B (2023) Beyond financial regulation of crypto-asset wallet software: in search of secondary liability. *Comput Law Secur Rev* 49:105829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2023.105829>
- Bargoni A, Ferraris A, Bresciani S, Camilleri MA (2022a) Crowdfunding and innovation: a bibliometric review and future research agenda. *Eur J Innov Manag*, ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-06-2022-0310>
- Bargoni A, Ferraris A, Bresciani S, Camilleri MA (2022) Crowdfunding and innovation: a bibliometric review and future research agenda. *Eur J Innov Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-06-2022-0310>
- Basu S, Basu K, Austin TH (2022) Crowdfunding non-fungible tokens on the blockchain. In: *Communications in computer and information science*, 1536 CCIS, pp 109–125. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-96057-5_8
- Baumgardner T, Neufeld C, Huang PC-T, Sondhi T, Carlos F, Talha MA (2017) Crowdfunding as a fast-expanding market for the creation of capital and shared value. *Thunderbird Int Bus Rev* 59(1):115–126. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tie.21766>
- Bayram O, Talay I, Feridun M (2022) Can fintech promote sustainable finance? Policy lessons from the case of Turkey. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912414>
- Belleflamme P, Lambert T, Schwienbacher A (2014) Crowdfunding: tapping the right crowd. *J Bus Ventur* 29(5):585–609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2013.07.003>
- Bhatia A, Kiran C (2017) An insight into development and delivery of innovative products and services adopted by micro-finance institutions in India. *Int J Appl Bus Econ Res* 15(9):335–342
- Bhatia S, Tyagi SS (2021) Ethereum. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85131467628&doi=10.1002%2F9781119711063.ch4&partnerID=40&md5=74b04caeac5d89255da682706a1f0532>
- Bhatt A, Joshipura M, Joshipura N (2022) Decoding the trinity of Fintech, digitalization and financial services: an integrated bibliometric analysis and thematic literature review approach. *Cogent Econ Finance*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2114160>
- Block JH, Groh A, Hornuf L, Vanacker T, Vismara S (2021) The entrepreneurial finance markets of the future: a comparison of crowdfunding and initial coin offerings. *Small Bus Econ* 57(2):865–882. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-020-00330-2>
- Böckel A, Hörisch J, Tenner I (2021) A systematic literature review of crowdfunding and sustainability: highlighting what really matters. *Manag Rev Q* 71(2):433–453. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-020-00189-3>
- Bogusz CI, Laurell C, Sandström C (2020) Tracking the digital evolution of entrepreneurial finance: the interplay between crowdfunding, blockchain technologies, cryptocurrencies, and initial coin offerings. *IEEE Trans Eng Manag* 67(4):1099–1108. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2020.2984032>
- Bogusz CI, Laurell C, Sandström C, Sandström C (2020b) Tracking the digital evolution of entrepreneurial finance: the interplay between crowdfunding, blockchain technologies, cryptocurrencies, and initial coin offerings. *IEEE Trans Eng Manag* 67(4):1099–1108. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2020.2984032>

- Butticè V, Vismara S (2022) Inclusive digital finance: the industry of equity crowdfunding. *J Technol Transf* 47(4):1224–1241. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-021-09875-0>
- Butticè V, Collewaert V, Stroe S, Vanacker T, Vismara S, Walthoff-Borm X (2022) Equity crowdfunders' human capital and signal set formation: evidence from eye tracking. *Entrep Theory Pract* 46(5):1317–1343. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10422587211026860>
- Cai CW (2018) Disruption of financial intermediation by FinTech: a review on crowdfunding and blockchain. *Account Finance* 58(4):965–992. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acfi.12405>
- Callon M, Courtial JP, Laville F (1991) Co-word analysis as a tool for describing the network of interactions between basic and technological research: the case of polymer chemistry. *Scientometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02019280>
- Camilleri MA, Bresciani S (2022) Crowdfunding small businesses and startups: a systematic review, an appraisal of theoretical insights and future research directions. *Eur J Innov Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-02-2022-0060>
- Campino J, Brochado A, Rosa Á (2021) Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs): the importance of human capital. *J Bus Econ* 91(8):1225–1262. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11573-021-01037-w>
- Campino J, Brochado A, Rosa Á (2022) Initial coin offerings (ICOs): Why do they succeed? *Financ Innov*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-021-00317-2>
- Cappa F (2022) Big data from customers and non-customers through crowdsourcing, citizen science and crowdfunding. *J Knowl Manag* 26(11):308–323. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-11-2021-0871>
- Caputo A, Kargina M, Pellegrini MM (2022) Conflict in virtual teams: a bibliometric analysis, systematic review, and research agenda. *Int J Confl Manag* 34(1):1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCMA-07-2021-0117>
- Chawla C (2020) Trust in blockchains: algorithmic and organizational. *J Bus Ventur Insights*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbvi.2020.e00203>
- Chen C (2006) CiteSpace II: detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature. *J Am Soc Inform Sci Technol* 57(3):359–377. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.20317>
- Chen Y (2018) Blockchain tokens and the potential democratization of entrepreneurship and innovation. *Bus Horiz* 61(4):567–575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2018.03.006>
- Chen X, Hu X, Ben S (2021) How individual investors react to negative events in the fintech era? Evidence from China's peer-to-peer lending market. *J Theor Appl Electron Commer Res* 16(1):52–70. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-18762021000100105>
- Coffie CPK, Zhao H (2021) Swapping the underlying technology of crowdfunding contracts for blockchain—the perspective of Roger's five perceived attributes of innovation. *Technol Anal Strat Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2021.1991571>
- Collomb A, De Filippi P, Sok K (2019) Blockchain technology and financial regulation: a risk-based approach to the regulation of ICOs. *Eur J Risk Regul* 10(2):263–314. <https://doi.org/10.1017/err.2019.41>
- Custers B, Overwater LJ (2019) Regulating initial coin offerings and cryptocurrencies: a comparison of different approaches in nine jurisdictions worldwide. *Eur J Law Technol*. <https://ejlt.org/index.php/ejlt/article/view/718>
- Dai H, Zhang DJ (2019) Prosocial goal pursuit in crowdfunding: evidence from kickstarter. *J Mark Res* 56(3):498–517. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022243718821697>
- Dal Mas F, Dicuonzo G, Massaro M, Dell'Atti V (2020) Smart contracts to enable sustainable business models. A case study. *Manag Decis* 58(8):1601–1619. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-09-2019-1266>
- Dapp T, Slomka L, Deutsche Bank AG, Hoffmann R (2015) Fintech reloaded—Traditional banks as digital ecosystems. In: Publication of the German original, pp 261–274
- Delina LL (2023) Fintech RE in a global finance centre: expert perceptions of the benefits of and challenges to digital financing of distributed and decentralised renewables in Hong Kong. *Energy Res Soc Sci* 97:102997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.102997>
- Deng H, Huang RH, Wu Q (2018) The regulation of initial coin offerings in China: problems, prognoses and prospects. *Eur Bus Organ Law Rev* 19(3):465–502. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40804-018-0118-2>
- Diñçol D, Özcan P, Zachariadis M (2023) Regulatory standards and consequences for industry architecture: the case of UK Open Banking. *Res Policy* 52(6):104760. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2023.104760>
- Domingo R-S, Pineiro-Chousa J, Angeles López-Cabarcos M (2020) What factors drive returns on initial coin offerings? *Technol Forecast Soc Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.119915>
- Egger C, Moreno-Sanchez P, Maffei M (2019) Atomic multi-channel updates with constant collateral in bitcoin-compatible payment-channel networks. In: Proceedings of the ACM conference on computer and communications security, pp 801–815. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3319535.3345666>
- Eldridge D, Nisar TM, Torchia M (2021) What impact does equity crowdfunding have on SME innovation and growth? An empirical study. *Small Bus Econ* 56(1):105–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00210-4>
- Fosso Wamba S, Kala Kamdjoug JR, Epie Bawack R, Keogh JG (2020) Bitcoin, Blockchain and Fintech: a systematic review and case studies in the supply chain. *Prod Plan Control* 31(2–3):115–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2019.1631460>
- Gallemore C, Nielsen KR, Jespersen K (2019) The uneven geography of crowdfunding success: spatial capital on Indiegogo. *Environ Plan Econ Space* 51(6):1389–1406. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X19843925>
- Gavrilova JA, Kvitsinia NV, Kalashnikova NA (2020) Development of the institute of public procurement in modern Russia: between blockchain and administration. In: Inshakova AO, Inshakova EI (eds) *Competitive Russia: foresight model of economic and legal development in the digital age*. Springer, pp 388–394. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-45913-0_44
- Ghobadi S, Mathiassen L (2024) Developers' decision to navigate resource adversity in crowdfunded digital development projects. *Decis Support Syst* 177:114083. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2023.114083>
- Giudici P (2018) Fintech risk management: a research challenge for artificial intelligence in finance. *Front Artif Intell*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2018.00001>
- Gomber P, Koch J-A, Siering M (2017) Digital Finance and FinTech: current research and future research directions. *J Bus Econ* 87(5):537–580. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11573-017-0852-x>

- Gomber P, Kauffman RJ, Parker C, Weber BW (2018) On the fintech revolution: interpreting the forces of innovation, disruption, and transformation in financial services. *J Manag Inf Syst* 35(1):220–265. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2018.1440766>
- Gonzalez L (2020) Blockchain, herding and trust in peer-to-peer lending. *Manag Finance* 46(6):815–831. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-09-2018-0423>
- Gonzalez L (2023) Financial literacy in for-profit vs pro-social peer-to-peer lending. *Manag Finance* 49(2):315–337. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-07-2021-0329>
- Gorkhali A, Chowdhury R (2022) Blockchain and the evolving financial market: a literature review. *J Ind Integr Manag* 07(01):47–81. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S242486222150024X>
- Gruzina YM, Zeinalov AA, Ilienkov ND, Ilienkov DA (2016) Crowd investing as a perspective instrument of financing small and middle-sized businesses in the Russian Federation. *J Appl Econ Sci* 11(8):1650–1660
- Guggenberger T, Schellinger B, von Wachter V, Urbach N (2023) Kickstarting blockchain: designing blockchain-based tokens for equity crowdfunding. *Electron Commer Res*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-022-09634-9>
- Gupta BB, Gaurav A, Panigrahi PK, Arya V (2023) Analysis of artificial intelligence-based technologies and approaches on sustainable entrepreneurship. *Technol Forecast Soc Change* 186:122152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122152>
- Hartmann F, Grotto G, Wang X, Lunesu MI (2019). Alternative fundraising: success factors for blockchain-based vs. conventional crowdfunding. In: IWBOSE 2019—2019 IEEE 2nd international workshop on blockchain oriented software engineering, pp 38–43. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IWBOSE.2019.8666515>
- Hartmann J, Hasan O (2022) Privacy considerations for a decentralized finance (DeFi) loans platform. *Clust Comput*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-022-03772-3>
- Hoffmann CH (2021) Blockchain use cases revisited: micro-lending solutions for retail banking and financial inclusion. *J Syst Sci Inf* 9(1):1–15. <https://doi.org/10.21078/JSSI-2021-001-15>
- Hua X, Huang Y, Zheng Y (2019) Current practices, new insights, and emerging trends of financial technologies. *Ind Manag Data Syst* 119(7):1401–1410. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-08-2019-0431>
- Huang Y, Bian Y, Li R, Zhao JL, Shi P (2019) Smart contract security: a software lifecycle perspective. *IEEE Access* 7:150184–150202. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2946988>
- Huang W, Meoli M, Vismara S (2020) The geography of initial coin offerings. *Small Bus Econ* 55(1):77–102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00135-y>
- Hughes H (2021) The complex implications of fintech for financial inclusion. *Law Contemp Probl* 84(1):115–128
- Islam MR, Rahman MM, Mahmud M, Rahman MA, Mohamad MHS, Embong AH (2021) A review on blockchain security issues and challenges. In: 2021 IEEE 12th control and system graduate research colloquium (ICSGRC), pp 227–232. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSGRC53186.2021.9515276>
- Jain R, Panchabudde H, Ranapurwala A, Kate A, Gaikwad A, Maroo H, Mishra Y (2024) Crowdfunding system based on blockchain. *Genze Int J Eng Technol (GIJET)* 10(1). <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&profile=ehost&scope=site&authtype=crawler&jrnl=23955287&AN=175658161&h=HwByoS1FR949TFm%2BluKd1BRiU5T%2Bg%2FQzVfeF51beL5fjJezr7h2fSA83vxYyEwL%2FEA8cwG6U%2BmS8nuqgAqzVA%3D%3D&cr=c>
- Jeyasheela Rakkini MJ, Geetha K (2021) Blockchain-enabled microfinance model with decentralized autonomous organizations. *Lect Notes Data Eng Commun Technol* 58:417–430. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-9647-6_32
- Kamilaris A, Fonts A, Prenafeta-Boldú FX (2019) The rise of blockchain technology in agriculture and food supply chains. *Trends Food Sci Technol* 91:640–652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2019.07.034>
- Khatter H, Chauhan H, Trivedi I, Agarwal J (2021) Secure and transparent crowdfunding using blockchain. In: 2021 6th International conference on recent trends on electronics, information, communication and technology, RTEICT 2021, pp 76–80. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RTEICT52294.2021.9573956>
- Kim J-H (2015) Understanding narrative inquiry: the crafting and analysis of stories as research. SAGE Publications
- Kim K-J, Hong S-P (2017) Design and implementation of system for reliable application using blockchain: a case study in P2P crowdfunding. *Int J Grid Distrib Comput* 10(12):81–92. <https://doi.org/10.14257/ijgcd.2017.10.12.08>
- Kim K, Park J, Pan Y, Zhang K, Zhang X (2022) Risk disclosure in crowdfunding. *Inf Syst Res* 33(3):1023–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2021.1096>
- Koh L, Dolgui A, Sarkis J (2020) Blockchain in transport and logistics—paradigms and transitions. *Int J Prod Res* 58(7):2054–2062. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2020.1736428>
- Kolbe M, Mansouri S, Momtaz PP (2022) Why do video pitches matter in crowdfunding? *J Econ Bus*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconbus.2022.106081>
- Kotsialou G, Mahmoodi T, Riley L, McBurney P, Pearce R, Dhillon A, Massey P (2018) Using Distributed Ledger Technology for shareholder rights management. In: Proceedings of the international joint conference on autonomous agents and multiagent systems, AAMAS, vol 3, pp 1986–1988. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054735413&partnerID=40&md5=4c60c51793e04eab5f7be1a17a42c84e>
- Kuppuswamy V, Bayus BL (2018) Crowdfunding creative ideas: the dynamics of project backers. In: Cumming D, Hornuf L (eds) *The economics of crowdfunding: startups, portals and investor behavior*. Springer, pp 151–182. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66119-3_8
- Laatikainen G, Semenov A, Zhang Y, Abrahamsson P (2020) ICO crowdfunding: incentives, pricing strategy, token strategy and crowd involvement. In: *Lecture notes in business information processing, LNBI*, vol 396, pp 32–40. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58858-8_4
- Leung XY, Sun J, Bai B (2017) Bibliometrics of social media research: a co-citation and co-word analysis. *Int J Hosp Manag* 66:35–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2017.06.012>
- Li G, Wang J (2019) Threshold effects on backer motivations in reward-based crowdfunding. *J Manag Inf Syst* 36(2):546–573. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2019.1599499>
- Li B, Xu Z (2021) Insights into financial technology (FinTech): a bibliometric and visual study. *Financ Innov* 7(1):69. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-021-00285-7>
- Liu J, Li X, Wang S (2020) What have we learnt from 10 years of fintech research? A scientometric analysis. *Technol Forecast Soc Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120022>

- Liu Y, Zhang S, Chen M, Wu Y, Chen Z (2021) The sustainable development of financial topic detection and trend prediction by data mining. *Sustainability* (Switzerland). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147585>
- Lukita C, Hatta M, Harahap EP, Rahardja U (2020) Crowd funding management platform based on block chain technology using smart contracts. *J Adv Res Dyn Control Syst* 12(2):1928–1933. <https://doi.org/10.5373/JARDCS/V12I2/S20201236>
- Mahajan Y, Srivastava S (2019) Holistic credit rating system for online microlending platforms with blockchain technology. *Commun Comput Inf Sci* 969:605–616. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-5826-5_47
- Mas I, Chuen DLK (2015) Bitcoin-like protocols and innovations. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84940434626&doi=10.1016%2fB978-0-12-802117-0-00021-7&partnerID=40&md5=2f349518b3dad5c261389365f69562b5>
- Matte J, Maier C, Reis L (2021) Security token offerings: a risk as feelings theoretic perspective on investment. In: International conference on information systems, ICIS 2020—making digital inclusive: blending the local and the global. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85103440214&partnerID=40&md5=f741c3a888d44b87312587cc206a3c48>
- Mbodji FN, Mendy G, Mbacke AB, Ouya S (2020) Proof of concept of blockchain integration in P2P lending for developing countries. In: Lecture notes of the institute for computer sciences, social-informatics and telecommunications engineering, LNICST, vol 311, pp 59–70. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-41593-8_5
- Meoli M, Vismara S (2022) Machine-learning forecasting of successful ICOs. *J Econ Bus* 121:106071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconbus.2022.106071>
- Meyskens M, Bird L (2015) Crowdfunding and value creation. *Entrep Res J* 5(2):155–166. <https://doi.org/10.1515/erj-2015-0007>
- Mhlanga D (2023) Block chain technology for digital financial inclusion in the industry 4.0, towards sustainable development? *Front Blockchain*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbloc.2023.1035405>
- Milian EZ, Spinola MDM, Carvalho MMD (2019) Fintechs: a literature review and research agenda. *Electron Commer Res Appl*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elelap.2019.100833>
- Momtaz PP (2021) Entrepreneurial finance and moral hazard: evidence from token offerings. *J Bus Ventur*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2020.106001>
- Mostafa MM, Feizollah A, Anuar NB (2022) Fifteen years of YouTube scholarly research: knowledge structure, collaborative networks, and trending topics. *Multimed Tools Appl*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-022-13908-7>
- Mougayar W (2016) *The business blockchain: promise, practice, and application of the next internet technology*. Wiley
- Mukkamala RR, Vatrupu R, Ray PK, Sengupta G, Halder S (2019) Converging blockchain and social business for socio-economic development. In: Proceedings—2018 IEEE international conference on big data, pp 3039–3048. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData.2018.8622238>
- Musleh AS, Yao G, Muyeen SM (2019) Blockchain applications in smart grid-review and frameworks. *IEEE Access* 7:86746–86757. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2920682>
- Nakamoto S (2008) Bitcoin: a peer-to-peer electronic cash system. *Decent Bus Rev*. <https://assets.pubpub.org/d8wct41f/31611263538139.pdf>
- Narayanan A, Bonneau J, Felten E, Miller A, Goldfeder S (2016) *Bitcoin and cryptocurrency technologies: a comprehensive introduction*. Princeton University Press
- Nehme M (2018) Regulating crowd equity funding—the why and the how. *J Law Soc* 45(1):116–135. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jols.12082>
- Nguyen LTQ, Hoang TG, Do LH, Ngo XT, Nguyen PHT, Nguyen GDL, Nguyen GNT (2021) The role of blockchain technology-based social crowdfunding in advancing social value creation. *Technol Forecast Soc Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120898>
- O'Dair M, Owen R (2019) Financing new creative enterprise through blockchain technology: opportunities and policy implications. *Strat Change* 28(1):9–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsc.2242>
- Oliva GA, Hassan AE, Jiang ZMJ (2020) An exploratory study of smart contracts in the Ethereum blockchain platform. *Empir Softw Eng* 25(3):1864–1904. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-019-09796-5>
- Panda SK (2020) Fraud-resistant crowdfunding system using ethereum blockchain. In: *Bitcoin and blockchain*. CRC Press.
- Pandey DK, Hassan MK, Kumari V, Zaied YB, Rai VK (2024) Mapping the landscape of FinTech in banking and finance: a bibliometric review. *Res Int Bus Financ* 67:102116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2023.102116>
- Paschen J (2017) Choose wisely: crowdfunding through the stages of the startup life cycle. *Bus Horiz* 60(2):179–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2016.11.003>
- Polas MRH, Kabir AI, Sohel-Uz-Zaman ASMd, Karim R, Tabash MI (2022) Blockchain technology as a game changer for green innovation: green entrepreneurship as a roadmap to green economic sustainability in Peru. *J Open Innov Technol Mark Complex* 8(2):62. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8020062>
- Rabbani MR, Khan S, Thalassinou EI (2020) FinTech, blockchain and Islamic finance: an extensive literature review. *Int J Econ Bus Adm* 8(2):65–86. <https://doi.org/10.35808/ijeba/444>
- Rashideh W (2020) Blockchain technology framework: current and future perspectives for the tourism industry. *Tour Manag* 80:104125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2020.104125>
- Rejeb A, Simske S, Rejeb K, Treiblmaier H, Zailani S (2020) Internet of Things research in supply chain management and logistics: a bibliometric analysis. *Internet Things* 12:100318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iot.2020.100318>
- Rejeb A, Keogh JG, Leong GK, Treiblmaier H (2021a) Potentials and challenges of augmented reality smart glasses in logistics and supply chain management: a systematic literature review. *Int J Prod Res* 59(12):3747–3776. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2021.1876942>
- Rejeb A, Keogh JG, Simske SJ, Stafford T, Treiblmaier H (2021b) Potentials of blockchain technologies for supply chain collaboration: A conceptual framework. *Int J Logist Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLM-02-2020-0098>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Keogh JG (2021) Cryptocurrencies in modern finance: a literature review. *Etikonomi*. <https://doi.org/10.15408/etk.v20i1.16911>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Simske S, Treiblmaier H (2021d) Blockchain technologies in logistics and supply chain management: a bibliometric review. *Logistics* 5(4):72

- Rejeb A, Treiblmaier H, Rejeb K, Zailani S (2021) Blockchain research in healthcare: a bibliometric review and current research trends. *J Data Inf Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42488-021-00046-2>
- Rejeb A, Abdollahi A, Rejeb K, Treiblmaier H (2022) Drones in agriculture: a review and bibliometric analysis. *Comput Electron Agric*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2022.107017>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Abdollahi A, Treiblmaier H (2022) The big picture on Instagram research: insights from a bibliometric analysis. *Telemat Inform*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2022.101876>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Simske SJ, Keogh JG (2022c) Blockchain technology in the smart city: a bibliometric review. *Qual Quant* 56(5):2875–2906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01251-2>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Alnabulsi K, Zailani S (2023) Tracing knowledge diffusion trajectories in scholarly bitcoin research: co-word and main path analyses. *J Risk Financ Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm16080355>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Appolloni A, Kayikci Y, Iranmanesh M (2023) The landscape of public procurement research: a bibliometric analysis and topic modelling based on Scopus. *J Public Procure*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOPP-06-2022-0031>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Appolloni A, Treiblmaier H (2023) Navigating the crowdfunding landscape: a study of knowledge trajectories based on main path analysis. *Eur J Innov Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-03-2023-0201>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Appolloni A, Treiblmaier H, Iranmanesh M (2024) Mapping the scholarly landscape of TikTok (Douyin): a bibliometric exploration of research topics and trends. *Digit Bus*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.digbus.2024.100075>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Appolloni A, Treiblmaier H, Iranmanesh M (2024b) Uncovering the themes and trends in crowdfunding research using Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *Manag Rev Q*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-024-00427-y>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Appolloni A, Seuring S (2024) Public procurement research: a bibliometric analysis. *Int J Public Sector Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPSM-07-2022-0157>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Appolloni A, Zailani S, Iranmanesh M (2024) Navigating the landscape of public–private partnership research: a novel review using latent Dirichlet allocation. *Int J Public Sector Manag*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPSM-09-2023-0263>
- Rejeb A, Rejeb K, Zrelli I, Süle E, Iranmanesh M (2024) Blockchain technology in the renewable energy sector: a co-word analysis of academic discourse. *Heliyon*. [https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440\(24\)05631-7](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440(24)05631-7)
- Reza-Gharehbagh R, Asian S, Hafezalkotob A, Wei C (2021) Reframing supply chain finance in an era of reglobalization: on the value of multi-sided crowdfunding platforms. *Transp Res Part E Logist Transp Rev* 149:102298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2021.102298>
- Rizwan A, Mustafa F (2022) Fintech attaining sustainable development: an investor perspective of crowdfunding platforms in a developing country. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127114>
- Rossi A, Vismara S (2018) What do crowdfunding platforms do? A comparison between investment-based platforms in Europe. *Eurasian Bus Rev* 8(1):93–118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40821-017-0092-6>
- Rossi A, Vanacker T, Vismara S (2023) Unsuccessful equity crowdfunding offerings and the persistence in equity fundraising of family business start-ups. *Entrep Theory Pract* 47(4):1327–1355. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10422587221121290>
- Roth J, Schär F, Schöpfer A (2021) The tokenization of assets: using blockchains for equity crowdfunding. In: Wendt K (ed) *Theories of change: change leadership tools, models and applications for investing in sustainable development*. Springer, pp 329–350. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52275-9_19
- Rrustemi J, Tuchschnid NS (2020) Fundraising campaigns in a digital economy: lessons from a Swiss synthetic diamond venture's initial coin offering. *Technol Innov Manag Rev* 10(6):53–63. <https://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1368>
- Saadat MN, Rahman SAHSA, Nassr RM, Zuhiri MF (2019) Blockchain based crowdfunding systems in Malaysian perspective. *ACM Int Conf Proc Ser*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313991.3313999>
- Sangwan V, Harshita P, Singh S (2020) Financial technology: a review of extant literature. *Stud Econ Financ* 37(1):71–88. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SEF-07-2019-0270>
- Schwarzc SL (2022) Regulating digital currencies: towards an analytical framework. *BUL Rev* 102:1037
- Seyedsayamdost E, Vanderwal P (2020) From good governance to governance for good: blockchain for social impact. *J Int Dev* 32(6):943–960. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.3485>
- Shelke P, Zanjali S, Patil R, Desai D, Chavan H, Kulkarni V (2022) Blockchain technology based crowdfunding using smart contracts. *Int Conf Augment Intell Sustain Syst (ICAIS)* 2022:939–943. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAIS55157.2022.10010749>
- Singh A, Rejeb A (2024) Illness perception: a bibliometric study. *Heliyon*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e31805>
- Sirisawat S, Chatjuthamard P, Kiattisin S, Treepongkaruna S (2022) The future of digital donation crowdfunding. *PLoS ONE*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0275898>
- Stekli J, Cali U (2020) Potential impacts of blockchain based equity crowdfunding on the economic feasibility of offshore wind energy investments. *J Renew Sustain Energy*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0021029>
- Suban SA (2022) Bibliometric analysis on wellness tourism—citation and co-citation analysis. *Int Hosp Rev* 37(2):359–383. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IHR-11-2021-0072>
- Subramanian H (2020) Security tokens: architecture, smart contract applications and illustrations using SAFE. *Manag Financ* 46(6):735–748. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-09-2018-0467>
- Sun Y, Li S, Wang R (2022) Fintech: from budding to explosion—an overview of the current state of research. *Rev Manag Sci*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00513-5>
- Swan M (2015) *Blockchain: blueprint for a new economy*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.
- Sweileh WM (2018) Research trends on human trafficking: a bibliometric analysis using Scopus database. *Glob Health* 14(1):106. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-018-0427-9>
- Tapscott D, Tapscott A (2016) *Blockchain revolution: How the technology behind bitcoin is changing money, business, and the world*. Penguin
- Tenner I, Hörisch J (2021) Crowdfunding sustainable entrepreneurship: what are the characteristics of crowdfunding investors? *J Clean Prod* 290:125667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125667>
- Thakor AV (2020) Fintech and banking: What do we know? *J Financ Intermed*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2019.100833>
- Treiblmaier H (2018) The impact of the blockchain on the supply chain: a theory-based research framework and a call for action. *Supply Chain Manag Int J* 23(6):545–559. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SCM-01-2018-0029>

- Turan SS (2015) Financial innovation—crowdfunding: Friend or foe? *Procedia Soc Behav Sci* 195:353–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.06.334>
- Vakilinia I, Badsha S, Sengupta S (2018) Crowdfunding the insurance of a cyber-product using blockchain. In: 2018 9th IEEE annual ubiquitous computing, electronics and mobile communication conference, UEMCON 2018, pp 964–970. <https://doi.org/10.1109/UEMCON.2018.8796515>
- Vismara S (2022) Expanding corporate finance perspectives to equity crowdfunding. *J Technol Transf* 47(6):1629–1639. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-021-09903-z>
- Wang Y, Kim D-K, Jeong D (2020) A survey of the application of blockchain in multiple fields of financial services. *J Inf Process Syst* 16(4):935–958. <https://doi.org/10.3745/JIPS.04.0185>
- Weinstein S, Barden P (2017) *The complete guide to fundraising management*. Wiley
- White HD, McCain KW (1998) Visualizing a discipline: an author co-citation analysis of information science, 1972–1995. *J Am Soc Inf Sci* 49(4):327–355. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4571\(19980401\)49:4%3c327::AID-ASI4%3e3.0.CO;2-4](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4571(19980401)49:4%3c327::AID-ASI4%3e3.0.CO;2-4)
- Wu W, Huang X, Wu C-H, Tsai S-B (2022) Pricing strategy and performance investment decisions in competitive crowdfunding markets. *J Bus Res* 140:491–497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.11.018>
- Xia Q, Gao J, Obiri IA, Asamoah KO, Woraie DA (2024) A secure data-sharing blockchain-based crowdfunding system. In: Attribute-based encryption (ABE): foundations and applications within blockchain and cloud environments, pp 229–245. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119989387.ch14>
- Xie Y, Holmes J, Dagher GG (2020) ZeroLender: trustless peer-to-peer bitcoin lending platform. In: CODASPY 2020—proceedings of the 10th ACM conference on data and application security and privacy, pp 247–258. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3374664.3375735>
- Yacoub G, Mitra P, Ratinho T, Fatalot F (2022) Sustainable entrepreneurs: What drives them to engage in different crowdfunding types? *Int J Entrep Behav Res* 28(4):980–1000. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBR-05-2021-0321>
- Yadav N, Sarasvathi V (2020) Venturing crowdfunding using smart contracts in blockchain. In: Proceedings of the 3rd international conference on smart systems and inventive technology, ICSSIT 2020, pp 192–197. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSSIT48917.2020.9214295>
- Yang H, Shao X, Wu M (2019) A review on ecosystem health research: a visualization based on CiteSpace. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11184908>
- Yasar B (2021) The new investment landscape: equity crowdfunding. *Central Bank Rev* 21(1):1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbrev.2021.01.001>
- Yu D, Yan Z, He X (2022) Capturing knowledge trajectories of mobile learning research: a main path analysis. *Educ Inf Technol* 27(5):7257–7280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10869-6>
- Zhang J, Zhang X, Liu W, Ji M, Mishra AR (2022) Critical success factors of blockchain technology to implement the sustainable supply chain using an extended decision-making approach. *Technol Forecast Soc Chang* 182:121881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121881>
- Zhang X, Lyu H, Luo J (2021) What contributes to a crowdfunding campaign's success? Evidence and analyses from GoFundMe data. *J Soc Comput* 2(2):183–192. <https://doi.org/10.23919/JSC.2021.0010>
- Zhu H, Zhou ZZ (2016a) Analysis and outlook of applications of blockchain technology to equity crowdfunding in China. *Financ Innov*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-016-0044-7>
- Zichichi M, Contu M, Ferretti S, D'Angelo G (2019) LikeStarter: a smart-contract based social DAO for crowdfunding. In: INFOCOM 2019—IEEE conference on computer communications workshops, INFOCOM WKSHPS 2019, pp 313–318. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INFOCOMW.2019.8845133>
- Zohar A (2015) Bitcoin: under the hood. *Commun ACM* 58(9):104–113. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2701411>
- Zou W, Lo D, Kochhar PS, Le X-BD, Xia X, Feng Y, Chen Z, Xu B (2021) Smart contract development: challenges and opportunities. *IEEE Trans Softw Eng* 47(10):2084–2106. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2019.2942301>
- Zrelli I, Rejeb A, Abusulaiman R, AlSahafi R, Rejeb K, Iranmanesh M (2024) Drone applications in logistics and supply chain management: a systematic review using latent Dirichlet allocation. *Arab J Sci Eng*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-023-08681-0>

Publisher's Note

Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.